

Factors influencing food environments

Deliverable D2.2

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DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
DMP	Data management plan	
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
SECURITY	Deliverables related to security issues	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	

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Acronyms and abbreviations

Terms	Definition
CFIR	The Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research
CWGs	Consultation and Working Groups
D	Deliverable
EPHA	European Public Health Alliance
EU	European Union
EUFIC	The European Food Information Council
F&V	Fruits and Vegetables
FEE	Foundation for Environmental Education
FFQ	Food frequency questionnaire
HFI	Healthy food store interventions
HFSS	Foods high in fat, salt, and/or sugar
HIB	High impact behaviours
INRAE	The French National Institute for Agriculture, Environment and Food Research
IR	Internal report
JLU	Giessen University
KUL	KU Leuven
LLs	Living Labs
NCDs	Non-Communicable Diseases
NEMS-P	The Perceived Nutrition Environment
SES	Socio-economic status
SPG	Survey, Protocols, Guidelines
SSB	Sugar-sweetened beverages
WP	Work package
WUR	Wageningen University

1. Part 1 - Introduction

The PLAN'EAT project will aim at implementing a multi-actor approach at three levels; macro (food system), meso (food environment) and micro (individual). This report presents a meso-analysis of barriers and enablers influencing food environments and dietary behaviour will present the findings from task 2.3 of the PLAN'EAT project. Task 2.3 builds on existing knowledge and the project's previous mappings of dietary patterns and food environments, and aims to analyse the influence of social and physical food environments on selected high impact diet behaviours. In doing so, task 2.3 consists of two parts;

- **Subtask 2.3.1, *Barriers and enablers of food chain actors to shape better food environments***, which is led by KU Leuven (KUL).

In this subtask, members of five collaborative working groups (CWG) in PLAN'EAT representative of the European food chain actors (farmers, food industries, retailers, food services and restaurants) were involved in an explorative study aimed at identifying the determinants (enablers and barriers) they experienced in producing and offering healthy and sustainable food. Indeed, the implementation process and the expected outcomes of interventions involving food chain actors aim to make the food environment healthier and more sustainable, are influenced positively and negatively by multiple determinants come from different sources, both internal and external to the organisation in which the intervention is tested and implemented. For this reason, the determinants indicated by the CWG's members, have been categorised into 5 main domains of origin related the characteristics of: 1) the organization where the intervention is implemented; 2) the context outside the organization; 3) the intervention; 4) the process planned to implement the intervention 5) actors involved in the implementation process. For each domain of origin, key challenges and leverage points about food supply, customer demand, financial implications, legislative requirements, accessibility of raw material and products have been identified.

- **Subtask 2.3.2, *Influences of social and physical food environments on dietary behaviour***, which is led by EUFIC.

In this subtask, a survey (SPG6), based in part on the typology of archetype EU food environments, was designed by EUFIC in collaboration with EPHA, INRAE, and FEE with the aim of analyzing the influence of food offer, food communication and food education on high impact dietary behaviours. Key factors such as availability, prices, accessibility, marketing, labelling, affordability, desirability, convenience, and origin were assessed. The role of education through its curriculum and school practices will also be examined. The SPG6 survey was distributed to LL citizen panels, whereafter EUFIC gathered all results into a meso-analysis report of barriers and enablers influencing food environments and dietary behaviour, that will feed into developing strategies respectively minimising and maximising their effects.

The results of these two subtasks will be presented below in two separate sections.

2. Part 2 –Barriers and enablers of food chain actors to shape better food environments

By Erik Mathijs and Francesca Vespa, KUL

2.1 Introduction

The impact of the food environment on dietary choices and diet-related health is a relatively new area of research. However, it is increasingly recognised that dietary behaviour is influenced by the environments in which people live, learn, work and play (Moran et al., 2020). This environment includes the 'community environment', which refers to the food sources available at community level, and the 'consumer environment', which refers to the product range, presentation and pricing at each source (Glanz et al., 2005; Caspi et al., 2012). In Western countries, stores are the primary food sources in the community environment. In addition, research shows that the consumer environment has a significant impact on dietary behaviour. Therefore, the consumer environment in food stores represents a key point of influence on dietary behaviour and a significant opportunity for dietary intervention (Middel et al., 2019). As a result, public health interventions are increasingly focusing on these environments. Compared to nutrition interventions targeted at individuals or groups, upstream interventions that modify the environments in which food and beverage choices are made may be more effective in improving health. (Moran et al., 2020)

Healthy Food Store Interventions (HFIs) are marketing strategy-based interventions that aim to promote nutritious food choices in stores and have been shown to have at least a positive impact on dietary behaviour (Moran and Roberto, 2020). HFIs rely on the '4Ps' of marketing (price, product, promotion and placement) used by food actors (retailers, restaurants, food service managers) (Glanz et al., 2012; Roy et al., 2015; Mah et al., 2019; Karpyn et al., 2020; Barrett et al., 2023). Possible HFIs related to the 4Ps, which can be linked to a single P or to several P's at the same time, are as follows:

- **Promotion** relates to informing the consumer about products. It is about what kind of information is (or is not) provided, such as nutritional or environmental information (e.g., Nutriscore, GHG emissions, true cost) in simple or elaborated ways. It is also about how that information is spread: via the product (e.g., info on the package), where the product is being purchased (e.g., restaurant menus, in-store signages, leaflets, taste tests) or through various ways of advertising (mass media, magazines, streets). Consumers may be nudged into certain more healthy/sustainable product/meal choices through information.
- **Price** refers to the price actually paid for a product. Prices can be lowered for promotional reasons (e.g., discounts).
- **Product**-related interventions relate to the availability and/or the composition of products, which may relate to the ingredients of a product or meal, portion sizes, packaging.
- **Place** refers to the physical location of products/meals in the food environment in shelves and/or counters. Consumers may be nudged into certain more healthy/sustainable product/meal choices by providing more visibility to healthy/sustainable alternatives and less to less healthy/sustainable alternatives.

However, in the implementation of successful HFIs that aim to encourage healthier/more sustainable purchases or discourage unhealthy/unsustainable ones, key actors involved in the implementation of the intervention face challenges that limit the optimisation of the implementation process and thus affect the expected outcomes of the intervention (health effects, sales effects or process measures) (Kerins et al., 2020).

To evaluate the determinants of implementation, the CFIR (Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research) serves as a tool for researchers to link the implementation process with outcomes (Damschroder et al., 2009). The CFIR is designed to be adaptable and applicable across various settings, ensuring consistency in the evaluation. Besides helping researchers determine what works or doesn't in implementation research, the CFIR provides insights into why and how implementation processes succeed or fail with a qualitative approach. The framework comprises 26 constructs (including 14 sub-constructs) divided into five main

domains of origin of the determinants in the implementation process that influence outcomes: characteristics of individuals, inner setting, intervention characteristics, outer setting, and process (Tinc et al., 2018).

In literature, there are not so many studies that evaluate the implementation process of interventions aiming at promoting healthier dietary behaviours changing the consumer environment, through the lens of perspectives and needs of food chain actors (Jalali et al., 2018; Winkler et al., 2020). Furthermore, the CFIR framework has been adapted to the food environment context and applied as evaluation tool mostly to the retail food environment, that is, the environment in which restaurants, food services and retail managers determine what and how a product is available at a given price.

Task 2.3.1 aimed to evaluate the determinants of the implementation of interventions aimed to promote healthy dietary behaviours in five different food environments, involving members of five collaborative working groups (CWG) that represent the European food chain actors (farmers, food industries, retailers, food services and restaurants) in PLAN'EAT. An explorative study conducted with the CWG leaders (ZLTO, SPES, FEE, VMZ and CREA) was designed to:

- Assess the knowledge and awareness of the CWG members about healthy and sustainable food;
- Explore the determinants that CWG members perceive as facilitating and/or inhibiting to the implementation of interventions in their food environment.

Task 2.3.1 was designed to carry out an ex-ante evaluation of the factors perceived by CWG members as hindering or facilitating the success of an intervention aimed at promoting healthier or more sustainable dietary behaviour, acting on the consumer environment that characterises the food environment. The results of Task 2.3.1 will feed into the formulation of the protocol for the CWGs and living labs for Task 4.2.

2.2 Methodology

The study consisted of three parts. A study of the literature about the determinants experienced by retailers, owners and interventionists in the implementation of HFIs was conducted to generate a long list of barriers and enablers. From the long list of barriers and enablers, the CWG leaders selected and compiled a short list of key determinants that best represented the characteristics of the food environments in which the CWG members operate. From these shortlists, CWG members were asked to indicate which of the determinants proposed are perceived as barriers or enablers in implementing interventions to make their food environments healthier and more sustainable.

Study of the literature

The first part of the study was to gain an understanding of interventions already tested and evaluated in literature, aimed at encouraging healthier eating behaviours through changes in the food environment, such as changes in pricing, availability, promotion or advertising of healthy and sustainable foods. The systematic review of Middel et al. (2019) was used as a reference to collect a list of the HFIs implemented in food stores (small store, supermarket, corner store and convenience store) published in 41 original studies. Middel et al. summarised the perceptions and experiences of the food store organisation's actors involved in the process and design of the various HFIs, identifying the determinants in the implementation of interventions. The determinants defined as 'barriers' had a negative impact on the implementation or on outcomes of the intervention; while the one defined as 'enablers' had a positive impact on the implementation or outcomes of the intervention.

Barriers and enablers were categorized according to domains of origins and themes, following the CFIR framework:

1. The **outer setting** represents the environment outside the intervention food-store. The themes identified in this domain, include determinants (barriers and enablers) related to: the product supply, consumer characteristics, community relations, competition, legislation, and media.
2. The **inner setting** characterizes the food store organisations, where interventions are implemented. The themes and subthemes (between brackets) identified in this domain,

- include determinants (barriers and enablers) related to: culture, (*commercial and health values*), structure (*physical, operational, financial, and knowledge structures*), and practices (*stocking and waste management*).
3. The **characteristics of the intervention**. The intervention domain encompasses all the component defining the intervention. The themes and *subthemes* (between brackets) identified in this domain, include determinants (barriers and enablers) related to: general characteristics (*context-intervention fit, flexibility, and complexity*), components (*support, promotion, staff training, customer education, and pricing*), and costs and benefits (*costs and risks, commercial benefits, and health benefits*).
 4. The **implementation process**. Process domain includes all the activities towards implementing the intervention. The themes identified in this domain, include determinants (barriers and enablers) related to: engagement, collaboration, communication, and organisation of activities.
 5. The **actors** who operate the inner setting. Actors plays an active role in the implementation of the intervention. How the actors involved in the intervention, their attitude and personality influence the outcomes of the intervention.

The list of determinants provided by the systematic review conducted by Middel et al. is available in Appendix A.

Adaptation to the CWG context

In order to adapt the results of Middel et al. to the five different consumer environments in which the CWG members operate by producing, processing and supplying food, KUL carried out one-on-one consultation with the CWG leaders. During the consultation, the long list of determinants that can influence the success or failure of HFIs in the food stores identified by Middel et al., was presented to the CWG leaders, who were then asked to identify the determinants that their members (farmers, food industries, retailers, food services and restaurants) may have experienced when implementing interventions aimed at promoting healthier and more sustainable food choices through the adoption of HFIs or, in the case of farmers, sustainable farming practices. Following the consultations, each CWG leader selected the determinants that best fitted the context of their members and compiled a short list of determinants from the long list provided by Middel et al. The short lists of determinants selected by each CWG leader are available in Annex A.

Open-ended survey (SPG5)

CWG leaders were asked to conduct an open-ended survey to validate the determinants (barriers and enablers) in the short list they had selected to conduct an open-ended survey with their members. The objectives of the open-ended survey were: 1) to assess CWG members' knowledge and awareness of healthy and sustainable food; 2) to understand whether the determinants selected by CWG leaders had been tested by members in implementing actions to make their 'consumer environments' healthier and more sustainable. In addition, CWG members were asked to indicate whether the proposed determinants were experienced as barrier or enabler in the implementation of the interventions.

CWG leaders surveyed their members in two ways: individual interviews (online survey) or group discussions (webinar/workshop). A facilitation guide for conducting the open-ended survey was provided (Annex B). The number of participants involved in SPG5 in each CWG group, and the methodology used by the CWG leaders are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Number of participants in the SPG5 in each of the CWGs and methodology used			
CWG group	Total number of members	Members involved in SPG5	Methodology used
Restaurants	26	8	Workshop
Retailers	2	4	Online survey
Farmers	25	17	Workshop
Food services	22	18	Online survey + 1:1 online interview
Food industries	51	51	Online survey

The CWG’s retailers consists of 2 members, but for SPG5 the CWG leader (CREA) decided to include 2 retailers who are part of the Living Labs in Sweden and Spain.

2.3 Results

The determinants identified by CWG members as barriers or enablers have been classified according to the CFIR framework (Damschroder et al., 2009). Each determinant has been classified into themes that characterise the five main domains of origins: inner setting, outer setting, intervention characteristics, process characteristics, actors. In this way, for each CWG, the domains of origin of the determinants that influence the success or failure of interventions that foresee changes in the consumer environment of CWG members, were characterised. The characterisation of the domains of origin of the determinants for each group of food chain actors allows us to identify which are the difficulties that influence the decision of supply chain actors to adopt and implement an intervention, and which are the enablers that would make them more willing to carry out these types of interventions. The determinants indicated by the CWG members are reported in the following paragraphs dedicated to each CWG.

2.3.1 RESTAURANTS

CWG restaurants comprises 26 establishments spread across 10 different countries, which required the organisation of different workshops based on languages. A total of 3 workshops were conducted between November and December 2023. The restaurants were invited by email to their respective workshops below:

- French speaking restaurants – 1 participating restaurant + 2 stakeholders (Experts working with restaurants on sustainability practices) + 1 Green Key Coordinator
- English speaking workshop gathering Hungarian, German and Irish restaurants – 5 participating restaurants
- Spanish speaking restaurants – 2 participating restaurants

Given availability constraints, restaurants unable to attend any workshops received the questionnaire, covering the same topics addressed in the workshop by email, to have the opportunity to share their opinion.

Exploring knowledge

The initial part of the discussion focused on evaluating knowledge and awareness of restaurants owners and/or chefs concerning healthy and sustainable food offers. It explores these two dimensions independently and as a general concept. Participants defined healthy food by emphasizing the benefits for the body and highlighting balanced nutrition and energy. The consensus leaned towards natural and unprocessed food with low sugar, low calories, and no additives. Sustainability was here as well a key criterion, with an emphasis

on minimal human intervention (e.g., using pesticides), and on seasonal and local produce. Participants defined sustainable food as locally, seasonally produced, highlighting a production process that avoids environmental harm, and respects biodiversity and animal welfare. Key terms mostly quoted were low environmental impact, no pesticides, plant-based, zero waste, ethical and fair remuneration. In this sample of restaurant owners, the discussions and responses indicated that they seemed well-informed on healthy and sustainable topics. Restaurant owners of this sample viewed healthy food as encompassing the environmental dimension as well, and some had underscored that sustainability in food involves not only environmental aspects but also social and economic dimensions.

Exploring barriers and enablers

Barriers and potential enablers that CWG restaurants faced in offering sustainable and healthy food were identified. Table 1 of Annex C summarizes all identified barriers and facilitators, structured along the framework domains and their (sub)themes for the restaurants.

Outer setting

The outer setting represents the environment outside the intervention food-outlets. Identified themes were: Consumer characteristics (Healthy/sustainability perceived as expensive; Customers uninterested in health and sustainability, Customers lack health and sustainability knowledge) Product supply; Community relations; Legislation.

Consumer characteristics

Consumer characteristics were barriers. Restaurants often perceived a lack of customer interest in health (and sustainability): a) Customers who frequented restaurants did so with the intention of indulging themselves, reflecting a consumer behaviour that prioritises pleasure over strict dietary/sustainability considerations. b) When eating out, customers particularly preferred to consume meat and products that are often out of season. c) Customers expressed dissatisfaction with plant-based meals. Furthermore, healthy (and sustainable) meals were perceived as expensive by customers: customers did not seem to prioritise sustainability when choosing a restaurant, leading to a general reluctance to pay higher prices for healthy/sustainable food. Restaurants perceived a lack of consumer interest and knowledge about health (and sustainability): trends in gastronomy were a pressure factor that could give customers the wrong information (e.g. avocados were promoted as healthy but were not sustainably produced in Europe).

Product supply

Product supply was discussed as a barrier. In managing a significant volume of healthy and sustainable meals, restaurants had found it difficult to work with small local suppliers because they were unable to meet their demand for food throughout the year, and participants also reported that sustainable producers/suppliers were unreliable in some areas.

Community relations

Strong relationships between buyers, suppliers, and producers were identified by participants as potential enablers for adopting an intervention to provide healthier and more sustainable food. Community support was perceived as a potential enabler for the restaurants to increase the availability of healthier food/meals in the restaurants.

Legislation

The implementation of sustainable guidelines through labels such as Green Key could help to increase the offer of healthier and more sustainable meals.

Inner setting

The inner setting refers to the restaurant organisation where interventions are implemented. Identified (sub) themes were: Structures (Space constraints; Lack of relevant expertise; Limited time/ substantial time investment)

Structure

Structures were often described as important barriers. Many participants discussed capacity as a structural element: Lack of relevant expertise in defining healthy and sustainable food among chefs was perceived as a barrier, as was the limited time available to restaurant owners to identify suppliers able to provide good quality ingredients. Indeed, the participant stressed that working with chefs to create tasty menus that are in line with sustainability was a challenge: not enough knowledge about sustainable agricultural production methods was included in the initial training of professionals. Furthermore, chefs in the kitchen are not open to cook innovative dishes and experimenting in the kitchen with available ingredients so the restaurant can't propose in the menu, dishes with plant-based alternatives to meat and fish. In addition, the constant availability of non-seasonal produce throughout the year made it difficult to train chefs to cook only with seasonal ingredients. It was not easy for restaurants to find suppliers of sustainably produced food, especially local suppliers, and they reported that they did not have the time to thoroughly verify the accuracy of supplier information and to monitor the entire production and transport process, which can lead to the risk of working with suppliers who practice greenwashing. As a result, they do not fully trust their suppliers, especially as they do not have the time to conduct their own research to better achieve sustainability on the plate

Intervention

The intervention domain encompasses everything directly related to the intervention. Identified (sub)themes were: General characteristics (Simple to implement; Adaptation to the context), Components (Lack of intervention support, Staff training), and Costs and benefits (High running costs).

General characteristics

If the intervention is easy to implement, i.e. did not require managers and staff to acquire new skills and/or managers did not have to buy new machinery (kitchen tools, refrigerators, electronic equipment, etc.), restaurants are willing to accept the intervention. In this case, it is preferable for the intervention to be like those previously implemented and adaptable to the contexts, thus being designed based on the characteristics of the target group of consumers. Restaurants indicated that interventionists should train restaurant's staff to use sustainable practices in the kitchen and cook healthy meals.

Components of the intervention

Restaurants highlighted the lack of intervention support from government (local authorities) and European regulatory agencies. They perceived a lack of control in the application of some regulations to produce environmentally sustainable food and food safety standards by other actors in the food chain, e.g. on the use of endangered species, on the issuing of the organic label. So, the lack of confidence in the food they buy from suppliers is a barrier that can be overcome if they perceive that regulators are applying strict controls on the production and supply side by government authorities. The higher price of healthy and sustainable food is cited as a barrier. They reported that "the rise in inflation and increased VAT on food is contributing to an increase in overall costs for restaurants, which subsequently affects menu prices. This then makes it more difficult for establishments to afford sustainable food, which is already relatively more expensive".

2.3.2 FOOD SERVICES

18 CWG food service members participated in SPG5: 14 who completed an online questionnaire and 4 who were interviewed individually.

Exploring knowledge

The initial part of the discussion focused on evaluating knowledge and awareness of catering owners concerning healthy and sustainable food offers. Participants defined healthy diet as good for human health but also sustainable (good for the planet). It should provide the right amount of nutrient content, low calorie intake, and not include processed food. How meals are consumed and prepared is also important for the participants: a healthy meal consists of food prepared from scratch and eaten in a relaxed environment, taking the time to enjoy a proper meal. Participants defined sustainable food as locally, seasonally produced, and economically accessible. Sustainable food should be produced, processed and consumed in accordance with environmental, social and economic values and its production and consumption should not lead to food waste and not overburden the earth's ecosystem. Sustainable food should be tasty. A sustainable diet should be plant-based or have a meat-free day once a week.

Exploring barriers and enablers

Barriers and potential enablers that CWG's food services faced in offering sustainable and healthy food choices were identified. Table 2 of Annex C summarizes all identified barriers and facilitators, structured along the framework domains and their (sub)themes for the food services.

Outer setting

The outer setting represents the environment outside the intervention food services organization. Identified (sub)themes were: Consumer characteristics (customers lack health knowledge, consumers prefer unhealthy products, consumer willingness to pay), Product supply (challenges in product supply), Community relations (no support from the community), Legislation (supportive and targeted policy, governance, stakeholders' engagement, food services-community relations).

Consumer characteristics

Consumer characteristics presented barriers. Food services perceived that consumers: 1) have no knowledge on what healthy food is, 2) are more oriented towards convenience foods, fast food or traditional recipes and 3) are not willing to pay a higher price for healthy and sustainable meals. As a result, food services do not perceive a community interest in healthy eating. Participants perceived that there is limited access to and availability of healthy, locally produced food. During the interviews, participants clearly highlighted the need for supportive and targeted policies through financial support (financial incentives to implement the intervention) from the government as essential enablers to encourage food service companies to offer healthy and sustainable food. Strong stakeholder engagement and a relationship between food service and the community, so that the community is interested in healthy meals, are very powerful enablers in the outer setting. In addition, clear communication and relationships with suppliers were identified as important factors in the success of interventions.

Inner setting

The inner setting refers to the food service organisation where interventions are implemented. Identified (sub)themes were: Structure (High staff turnover) and Practices (Limited menu).

Structure

Capacity as a structural element was indicated as a barrier by participants. Capacity was sometimes limited further by high staff turnover rates, which made it difficult to train them.

Practices

Practices related to chefs' tendency to make the same recipes repeatedly are presented as a barrier to interventions aimed at increasing the availability of healthy options on the menu.

Intervention

Identified (sub)themes in the intervention domain, were: General characteristics (simple to implement; adaptation to the context), Components of the intervention (materials lack durability, improved skills for implementation process, building food services-supplier relationship), and Costs and benefits (high initial investments).

General characteristics

The general characteristic discussed as enablers by the food services were 'simple to implement' and 'adaptation to the context': for them, an intervention is successful if it is easy to implement and adapted to the context in which it is applied (considering the needs of consumers).

Components of the intervention

When implementing an intervention aimed at increasing the use of fresh products in the organization, the lack of knowledge among cooks on how to outlets fresh foods with a short shelf life was identified as a barrier. The higher price of healthy and sustainable food, which represents a high initial investment, was also identified as a barrier. Staff training was seen as an important enabler to implement an HFIs intervention.

Process

The process of an intervention refers to the collaborative activities towards implementing the intervention. One identified theme was clear communication. That is, clear communication between the interventionists and the actors involved in the intervention's implementation facilitates its success.

2.3.3 FOOD INDUSTRY

For the CWG food industry, SPG5 was carried out by sending a questionnaire to 92 companies. The majority of respondents consists of small- and medium-sized food and beverage companies located throughout Europe.

Exploring knowledge

The initial part of the discussion focused on evaluating knowledge and awareness of food industry owners concerning healthy and sustainable food offers. Participants defined healthy food as slightly processed, with a relatively low content of sugar, salt and saturated fat and providing health benefits to the consumer. The correct balance of nutrients and the right portion sizes are also important when it comes to healthy products. Healthy food is produced and processed in an environment compatible with EU cleaning and hygiene standards. Participants defined sustainable as a local, tasty, fresh food produced with technology and competence, but not GMO; accessible to everyone; with low environmental and social impact. The production of sustainable food should have a minimal waste impact and be use of renewable energy. The product must be produced with the minimum possible environmental footprint, without the addition of preservatives, and must meet a basic percentage of the daily nutritional requirements of a human being.

Exploring barriers and enablers

Barriers and potential enabler that CWG food industry faced in offering/producing sustainable and healthy food were identified. Table 3 (Annex C), summarizes all identified barriers and facilitators, structured along the framework domains and their (sub)themes for the food industries.

Outer setting

In the outer setting of the food industries, the (sub) themes identified, are: Consumer characteristics (open for innovation and experimentation, lower demand-healthy products, consumer prefer unhealthy products, consumers lack knowledge about healthy and sustainable food) Product supply (challenges in product supply), Legislation (legislation for innovative food, legal barriers, legislation for sustainable foods, promotion

legislation, certification), Collaboration (collaboration industry-research center; clear communication with consumers).

Consumer characteristics

Consumer characteristics presented barriers. Food industries perceived that costumer: 1) are not open to try new food/product (neophobia); 2) their preferences are driven by price: *low-cost food more preferred, especially by low-income consumers*; 3) no knowledge about the effect of food intake on their health and 4) no demand for healthy food in the market.

Legislation

The lack of legislation on how to commercialize and produce innovative food (i.e. insects), lack of a definition of sustainable food, determining the criteria for sustainability, and the strict requirements to obtain the label for the product produced were indicated as barriers in the production of healthy and sustainable food by the food industries. Furthermore, they pointed out *the lack of support from the professional community (especially the Ministry of Health and health institutes) to promote an educational campaign on how to approach a healthy and sustainable diet.*

Collaboration

Establishing clear communication with consumers, based on mutual trust, and sharing information about the characteristics of the food produced by the food industry was identified as an enabler to obtain community support that can incentivise the food industry to be more oriented towards the production of healthy and sustainable food. Furthermore, establishing collaborations with research centers was seen to boost scientific results on new proteins.

Inner setting

In the inner setting of the food industries, the (sub) themes identified, were: Structure (infrastructure, lack of relevant expertise); Product characteristics (sensory analysis, price, competition)

Structure

Barriers in the structure are related to inadequacies in the infrastructure (need for new technologies in the organization) and to the lack of relevant expertise among the staff i.e. how to avoid food waste.

Product characteristics

Barriers in producing healthy food using innovative technologies were faced by food industries also due to the product characteristics: healthy/sustainable food are not appealing (taste, smell, consistency) for consumers and are more expensive comparing to the unhealthy option (the price of packaging material affect the final price of the product) for these reasons, sustainable foods are not competitive in the market.

Intervention

For the intervention domain the (sub) theme identified were: costs and benefits (high initial investment, doubts regarding changing customer behavior, sales performance). Because of doubts about consumers' curiosity to try innovative foods, food industries cannot predict the sales performance of a healthy and sustainable food produced with high investment in new technologies, skilled workers and research & development. These aspects are therefore identified as barriers to the production of healthier and more sustainable food. As potential enablers, participants suggested that for an intervention to be effective, it must be adapted to the context: *enterprises must be able to offer higher quality products and improve customer satisfaction with these products.*

2.3.4 FARMERS

CWG farmers conducted the SPG5 survey and organised two webinars with 17 of their 25 members.

Exploring knowledge

The initial part of the discussion focused on evaluating knowledge and awareness of farmers concerning healthy and sustainable food/food production. Participants defined healthy food as nutritious, fresh, non-processed, locally and seasonally produced. Healthy food should promote the maintenance of a healthy body and mind and come from an ethical source and be made from natural materials. Healthy food should be part of a balanced diet and be cultivated without artificial inputs. For participants, foods containing genetically modified organisms cannot be sustainable. Sustainable foods are produced in an environmentally and socially conscious manner minimizing their effect on nature, water resources, soil and carbon emissions. They are produced with low input fertilizers and using good manure, in a sustainable farming system with an ecological-friendly approach. Sustainable food is produced locally, in small quantities but of high quality.

Exploring barriers and enablers

Barriers and potential enablers that CWG' farmers faced in offering/producing sustainable and healthy food were identified. Table 4 (Annex C), summarizes all identified barriers and facilitators, structured along the framework domains and their (sub)themes for the farmers.

Inner setting

In the inner setting of the farmers, the (sub) themes identified, were: Structure (lack of relevant expertise, limited time, technological limitation).

Structure

Structures were described as important barriers. Farmers reported: 1) lack of expertise to implement the intervention, usually the farmer and the staff need training courses or otherwise acquire new knowledge to implement an intervention 2) Interventions to encourage farmers to produce food using sustainable production methods have strict deadlines and do not take into account the necessary preparatory work in the field to start the intervention 3) technological limitation due to the lack of adequate storage machinery and methods.

Intervention

For the intervention domain the (sub) themes identified were: Components of the intervention (lack of intervention support, building retailer-farmer relationships); Cost and benefits (high running costs, doubts regarding changing consumer behavior, high production costs).

Components of the intervention

Farmers perceived they did not receive the necessary support from interventionists (advisors, government) during the implementation process: they highlighted the lack of technical support and regulatory constraints. Farmers suggested that during the implementation of the intervention, interventionists should communicate to farmers the characteristics of the intervention (budget, duration, support, methods of implementation) and provide training to farmers to facilitate the implementation of an intervention. The lack of interaction and cooperation with other actors in the supply chain and among farmers themselves also prevented farmers from adopting interventions to adapt their production to consumption trends.

Costs and benefits

Concerning the costs and benefits of implementing interventions to make their production more environmentally sustainable, farmers emphasized that the initial investment capital to carry out an intervention is usually very high: before starting the intervention, it is necessary to incur various expenses

(purchase of new machinery, modification of production, etc.). As the adoption of more sustainable practices in the field leads to reduced production, the higher production costs are not recovered.

Farmers were discouraged from implementing and investing in the intervention because they did not believe it could influence consumer demand for healthy and sustainable food. But a strong relationship between the farmer and the community was identified as an enabler by farmers: if the community supports the farmer and demands healthy and sustainable food production, the farmer is more likely to implement this type of intervention.

2.3.5 RETAILERS

CWG retailers includes four retailers: two big companies, one in Sweden (5000 employees) and one in Germany (400,000 employees), one SME in Italy (600 employees) and one small company in Spain (2 employees).

Exploring knowledge

The initial part of the discussion focused on evaluating knowledge and awareness of retailers concerning healthy and sustainable food offers. Retailers defined healthy food as organic and without negative impact on human health at the short, medium and long term. Healthy foods should be part of a balanced diet promoting fruit and vegetable intake, whole grains and fibre, while discouraging sugar, salt and saturated fatty acids intake. Sustainable foods were defined as local, organic, healthy and nutritious foods with a low environmental impact for the planet's resources and with a low negative social impact for the food supply chain. Sustainable food as a whole should be able to feed the global population while remaining within the planetary boundaries. A sustainable diet should prioritize animal welfare.

Exploring barriers and enablers

Barriers and potential enablers that CWG retailers faced in offering sustainable and healthy food were identified. Table 5 of Annex C summarizes all identified barriers and facilitators, structured along the framework domains and their (sub)themes for the retailers.

Outer setting

In the outer setting of the retailers, the (sub) themes identified, were: Consumer characteristics (sustainable perceived as expensive, consumer lack health knowledge, lower demand healthy/sustainable products, open for innovation and experimentation, consumer food choices); Legislation (legislation for sustainable foods, legislation for healthy foods, promotion legislation, legislation requirements).

Consumer characteristics

Consumer characteristics presented barriers. Retailers perceived that costumers: 1) are not (always) willing to pay more for sustainable products (even if they say so in questionnaires / before the purchase) 2) have their own definition of what is healthy due to their personal knowledge or due to habits that they often learned early on in their childhood 3) are sceptical about whether plant-based alternatives are healthy. Retailer stressed that the demand for sustainable products is sometimes not high enough to justify the shelf space needed for sustainable products.

Legislation

Legislation presented different types of barriers. Retailers claimed legislation for sustainable foods: there is no single universal definition of what sustainability really means, making it difficult for them to categorise and indicate which foods are sustainable in order to sell them. Similarly for healthy food, no clear guidance and definition of healthy food is provided by different institutions. Retailers also highlighted how the pending regulation of green claims at EU level and strict EU rules on retailers' advertising policies can make it difficult for them to decide on the right communication campaign to promote healthy food. Retailers believe that

educational campaigns are needed to inform the customer about which products to choose for adopting a more sustainable diet.

Inner setting

In the inner setting of the retailers, the (sub) themes identified were: Structure (limited financial resources). Limited financial resources to purchase new machinery was indicated as the only barriers in the inner setting by retailer to implement intervention faced in offering sustainable and healthy food in outlets.

Intervention

For the intervention domain the (sub) theme identified were: Cost and benefits (high running costs, substantial time investment, substantial effort or impractical); Collaboration (collaboration with competitors).

Costs and benefits

For retailers, the implementation of an intervention to increase the offer of healthy and sustainable food in outlets, have higher running costs because sustainable products are often more expensive than non-sustainable products and require substantial time investment for the promotional campaign of it and the frequent follow up during the implementation process. To make them more willing to adopt this type of intervention, financial incentives should be provided by the interventionists to support the running costs and the intervention should guarantee them economic benefits.

Collaboration

Competition from other retailers was cited as a barrier to adopting an intervention: Competitors could offer promoted products at better prices or provide an alternative for dissatisfied customers, leading to a loss of customers. Collaborations with other retailers and food chain actors was indicated as an enabler.

2.4 Conclusion

The conclusions reported below are intended to provide a summary of the most relevant results of the study conducted by the CWG leaders. When asked to define healthy and sustainable food, the responses from the various CWGs were fairly uniform: a healthy food product provides the right amount of nutrients needed for a healthy and balanced diet, which has a positive impact on physical and mental health. Healthy food is also sustainable and vice versa, as the two concepts are often linked. A food can be defined as sustainable if the natural, human and animal resources needed to produce it are reduced to a minimum. For most respondents, a healthy and sustainable product is unprocessed, locally produced and seasonal. While the CWG food industry members did not emphasize the "naturalness" of the product, their responses showed that they considered that processed products, including animal products, can be healthy and sustainable. The question on the definition of healthy and sustainable food was put to the CWGs in order to check their level of knowledge on healthy and sustainable foods/meals and to verify if there is a homogeneity of answers among the different actors in the food chain.

Compared to the five domains proposed by the Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR) to characterize the barriers that stakeholders may encounter when implementing interventions aimed at providing or producing healthy and sustainable food, three main domains emerged as relevant to all CWG members: outer setting, inner setting and intervention. In particular, the determinants that CWG members perceived as barriers to the implementation of HFIs were related to: 1) the characteristics of consumers, their low demand for healthier and more sustainable products, the lack of consumer knowledge about the benefits of these products, 2) the lack of clear European and national guidelines to support this type of intervention, 3) the structural and supply deficiencies of healthy and sustainable food. CWG members indicated that they need more support from experts for training in the management of healthy and sustainable products and for promoting healthy and sustainable food in a way that will be more attractive to consumers.

For CWG members the consumer's eating habits rooted in traditional cuisine and consumer's skepticism about healthy and sustainable cause by the low sensory appeal of it, are determinants that strongly influence negatively their decision to implement HFIs interventions type. Furthermore, CWGs have indicated the need to support higher cost to purchase (in the case of restaurant, retailer and food service) and to produce (food industry, farmers) healthy and sustainable products. The actions promoted and funded by European and national policies do not have common objectives, as European policies are poorly adapted to national guidelines, according to CWG members.

When looking at the enablers identified by the CWG members, it is clear that most of them belong to the outer setting rather than the inner setting. This means that most respondents are looking for incentives or subsidies from national or EU institutions. They would be more willing to adopt interventions that are simple to implement and do not require high running costs or the acquisition of new skills and machinery. During the process of implementing the intervention, CWGs suggested that intra- and inter-cooperation should be encouraged, and a strong community relationship with food actors, especially farmers, can motivate them to complete the specific HFIs intervention. Many of the enablers proposed by the CWG members highlight the need for food education campaigns for consumers who need to adapt to national culinary traditions.

Limitations

Subtask 2.3.1 does not provide results that can be generalized to all stakeholders and food chain actors in the European supply chain, as it is designed to collect opinions and information from Consultation and Working Groups (CWGs) involving a small number of food chain actors located in the 9 countries where the PLAN'EAT Living Labs are present. The results of Subtask 2.3.1 will then be used to develop case studies related to individual CWGs and will be integrated with the results of Task 4.2, where CWG members will be involved in the actual implementation of an intervention in the food environments in which they operate. The data collected in sub-task 2.3.1 will serve as an ex-ante evaluation of the determinants perceived by the CWGs as barriers or enablers to the implementation of an intervention aimed at promoting healthier and more sustainable dietary behavior by consumers, adopting some marketing strategies that respond to the objectives of the food chain actors and the business model of the food source they manage.

3. Part 3 – Influences of social and physical food environments on dietary behaviour

By Malou Reipurth and Betty Chang, EUFIC

3.1 Introduction

The chapter below will present the subtask 2.3.2, *Influences of social and physical food environments on dietary behaviour*, including the theoretical background, the method, the findings, and a conclusion.

3.1.1 FOOD ENVIRONMENTS OF THE LIVING LABS

As described above, the SPG6 survey should be based on the typology of archetype EU food environments presented in D1.3. In D1.3, the description of food environments was based on the conceptual model defined by Turner et al. (2018) of the food environment as “the interface that mediates people’s food acquisition and consumption within the wider food system. It encompasses external dimensions such as the availability, prices, vendor and product properties, and promotional information; and personal dimensions such as the accessibility, affordability, convenience and desirability of food sources and products”. Emphasis was put on food environments resulting from the interaction between external (e.g. marketing, retail and product properties, prices, and availability), and personal domains (e.g. convenience, acceptability, affordability) , as being part of wider food systems (as depicted in Figure 1).

Figure 1: Conceptual model of the food environment (Turner et al., 2018)

Promoting healthy and sustainable diets requires more than just educating consumers, as their choices are shaped by the food environments in which they make decisions. While most research has concentrated on the external aspects of the food environment, there is less understanding of how to evaluate its subjective

dimensions, i.e., how external aspects are perceived by consumers. In this study, the dimensions of food environments and food offer were explored through self-reported measures of respondents' perceptions. Food environments (also known as nutrition environments) are often separated into the community food environment and the consumer food environment, as depicted in Figure 2 below (Caspi et al., 2012; Glanz et al., 2005). This conceptual model of the nutrition environment developed by Glanz et al. (2005) focuses on the interaction between the community and consumer dimensions of food environments. This distinction is useful for differentiating between the distribution of food sources within a community and what consumers experience inside their usual food stores. For measuring this interplay, the Nutrition Environment Measurement Survey for perceived nutrition environments (NEMS-P) by Alber et al. (2018), which has been adapted to the various EU country contexts of the nine LLs (France, Germany, Spain, Greece, Italy, Ireland, Sweden, Hungary, and Poland), has been applied to the present survey to measure the perceived food environments. NEMS-P is grounded in social cognitive theory, which posits that individuals are shaped partly by their environment. The nutrition environments that people perceive and observe affect their eating behaviours directly and indirectly, through food shopping habits (such as shopping frequency and grocery planning) and the nutrition environment. This framework implies a connection between food shopping behaviours and the home food environment, which in turn, directly impacts eating behaviour. In this study, EUFIC adapted the NEMS-P questionnaire to align with the version used by KUL in their work on D1.3 and with the context of the LLs and with the aims the project tasks. The five dimensions of food environments (availability, accessibility, affordability, acceptability, and accommodation) (Glanz et al., 2005) were also considered in the questionnaire design.

Furthermore, the model by Glanz et al. (2005) considers the influence of the information environment (e.g. media, advertising) as well as the organizational environments (e.g., the food environment of their home, school, etc.), which corresponds with and has inspired the design and aim of this study.

Figure 2. Model of Community Nutrition Environments. Glanz et al., 2005

Additionally, several studies have delved into more nuanced aspects of the food environment (Charreire et al., 2010; McKinnon et al., 2009), exploring various other dimensions of food access such as availability, accessibility, affordability, acceptability, and accommodation adapted from Penchansky and Thomas (1981) healthcare model.

- **Availability** refers to the adequacy of the supply of healthy food. In the food environment, it might include the presence of certain types of restaurants near people's homes or the number of places to buy produce.
- **Accessibility:** This dimension is inherently geographic, referring to the location of the food supply and the ease of reaching it. Travel time and distance are key measures of accessibility.
- **Affordability** refers to food prices and people's perceptions of value relative to the cost.
- **Acceptability** refers to people's attitudes about attributes of their local food environment, and whether the available products meet their personal standards. As an attitudinal variable, it is ideally measured by surveying participants.
- **Accommodation**, or how well local food sources accept and adapt to local residents' needs. Although largely unexplored in existing literature, it could include factors such as store hours and types of payment accepted.

These five dimensions were considered in the design of the questionnaire to ensure that all aspects were explored.

3.1.2 HIGH IMPACT BEHAVIOURS

As mentioned earlier, the high impact behaviours (HIB) were determined in task 2.1. Led by JLU with the support of EUFIC, task 2.1 aimed to identify and select dietary behaviours with high impact potential that: a) had behaviour change potential (Behavioural Plasticity), b) were acceptable for target groups and stakeholders (Initiative Feasibility), and c) were within a safe operation space (regarding environmental, social, and health impacts) (Technical Potential) (Nielsen et al., 2020). Figure 3 below presents an overview of these factors and their association with each other and with high impact behaviours.

Figure 3. Factors affecting behaviour change potential

The goal was to end up with up to 5 high impact behaviours per LL. Figure 4 below shows an overview of the process of selecting these final high impact behaviours.

Figure 4. Overview of high impact behaviour selection process

As a first step, information on the country-specific dietary guidelines of each of the 9 LL countries was collected, also capturing environmental, social and health impacts. This information was applied to create an overview of country- and target group-specific dietary behaviours. In addition, the Planetary Health Diet (Willet et al., 2019) recommendations were included to add dietary behaviours relevant to the objectives of the PLAN'EAT project. This resulted in a total of 342 dietary behaviour items.

The next step was selecting the key behaviours that would serve as the basis for the subsequent surveys, determined by two factors: a) the dietary behaviour items with the greatest consistency across dietary guidelines in the LL countries, and b) the expertise of the entire JLU team. Those factors allowed inclusion of the dietary behaviours considered relevant by the majority of the LL countries and, in addition, inclusion of dietary behaviours relevant to the objectives of the PLAN'EAT project. Using this approach, 75 dietary behaviour items in 12 categories were determined.

To identify the final high impact behaviours, the following surveys were created and sent to various project partners:

1. Surveys for each of the 9 LL's
The survey was aimed at LL leaders' assessment of the *plasticity* (i.e., the likeliness that their target group would adopt the behaviour) and the *feasibility* (i.e., the likeliness that relevant stakeholders

would support the target group with adopting the behaviour) of the 75 dietary behaviours identified in the previous step

2. Surveys for experts of a) environmental, b) health and c) socio-economic and ethical impacts
The surveys were aimed at the respective experts' assessment of an *overall or average environmental, health, or socio-economic potentials* of the 75 dietary behaviours identified in the previous step. The environment, health and socio-economic surveys were filled in by representatives of the following organizations: EUFIC, SLU, CREA, EPHA, INRAE, UCD, ICONS, KUL, other (external).

As the next step, the evaluation of the LL ratings was linked to the evaluation of the expert ratings. Figure 5 below provides an overview of the resulting top rated 40 eating behaviours across LLs.

BEVERAGES

- B1** Drink 1.5-2L water (for an adult diet) per day
- B2** Choose tap water instead of bottled water
- B3** Choose to drink water instead of sugar-sweetened beverages
- B4** Choose to drink other unsweetened beverages (e.g., tea) instead of sugar-sweetened beverages
- B5** Choose organically produced beverages (e.g., tea, coffee, juice)
- B6** Limit alcoholic beverage consumption to a max. of up to 2 glasses/per day for men or 1 glass/per day for women
- B7** Do not drink alcohol at an age under 18 years

EGGS

- E1** Eat 2-4 servings of eggs per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 1 egg)

EATING BEHAVIOURS

- EB4** Accept a variety of foods

FISH

- F1** Eat (2-)3 servings of fish and seafood per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 125-150g)
- F3** Choose organically produced fish

FATS, SUGAR, AND SALT

- FS2** Choose vegetable oils (e.g., olive oil, rapeseed oil)
- FS3** Choose organically produced oils
- FS5** Limit the consumption of added sugars (e.g., from sweets) (max. 25 g for an adult diet per day)
- FS11** Limit consumption of processed food products high in salt, sugars, and fats (e.g., fast food, salty snacks, biscuits, bars)

GRAINS

- G1** Eat 3-6 servings of grain-based foods per day (1 serving for adult diet: e.g., 40-60 g bread/60-80 g dried pasta or rice)
- G2** Choose a variety of grain-based foods (e.g., flour types, pasta, rice etc.)
- G3** Choose primarily whole grains
- G4** Choose organically produced grains

LEGUMES

- L1** Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw/125 g cooked)
- L2** Choose a variety of legumes
- L3** Choose organically produced legumes

MEAT

- M1** Eat 0-3 servings of meat per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 100-125 g)
- M2** Limit the consumption of processed meat (both red and white meat) or even avoid it
- M3** Limit the consumption of red meat or even avoid it
- M4** Limit the consumption of all meats or even avoid it
- M5** Choose poultry instead of red/processed meat
- M9** Choose eggs instead of meat as an alternative source of protein
- M11** Choose plant-based alternatives (e.g., legumes, nuts) instead of meat as an alternative source of protein

NUTS AND SEEDS

- N1** Eat a small handful of nuts and seeds (2-)3 times a week (1 serving for an adult diet: 25 g)
- N2** Choose a variety of nuts and seeds

NUTRITIONAL NEEDS

- NN1** Know your energy (caloric) needs and eat accordingly (don't over-/under-eat)
- NN3** Ensure an adequate vitamin-D intake through sun exposure or supplementation (20 µg/d for an adult)

VEGETABLES AND FRUITS

- V1** Eat 5 servings of vegetables and fruits per day (1 serving for an adult diet: 125 g)
- V3** Choose a variety of vegetables and fruits
- V4** Choose organically produced vegetables and fruits
- V6** Choose seasonal vegetables and fruits

Figure 5. Top 40 eating behaviours. Coloured labelling of the single items according to their affiliation with food groups or eating behaviours

The final step involved a workshop bringing together JLU, EUFIC, and all nine LLs with the aim of performing a final selection of a maximum of 5 high impact behaviours per LL. Through a workshop with the LL leaders, each LL leader was given the option of choosing 3-5 high impact behaviours relevant for their LL from a list. Their chosen high impact behaviours for each LL are displayed in Table 3 below.

Table 3. High impact behaviours per LL										
HIB/LL	France	Germany	Greece	Hungary	Ireland	Italy	Poland	Spain	Sweden	Total
Meat 1 - reduce meat consumption (eat 0-3 portions/week)	x	x			x		x			4
Meat 2 - choose poultry instead of red/processed meat										0
Meat 3 - choose plant-based alternatives (e.g., legumes, nuts) instead of meat as an alternative source of protein (twice a week)				x						1
Meat 4 - limit the consumption of processed meat (both red and white meat) or even avoid it						x			x	2
Meat 5 - limit the consumption of red meat or even avoid it				x				x		2
F&V – Eat 5 servings of vegetables and fruits per day		x	x	x	x	x		x		6
Legumes – Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)	x		x		x	x	x	x	x	7
HFSS – Limit the consumption of ultra-processed food products high in added fat, salt & sugar	x	x	x		x	x				5
Salt – Limit salt (<1500 mg/day or 2/3 of teaspoon)			x							1
SSB – Drink water instead of sugar-sweetened beverages						x			x	2
Tap water - Choose tap water instead of bottled water							x			1
Energy needs - Know your energy (caloric) needs and eat accordingly (don't over-/under-eat)					x					1
Total	3	3	4	3	5	5	3	3	3	32

3.1.3 INTERVENTIONS

The PLAN'EAT Internal Report (IR1), "*Behaviour change strategies to change dietary behaviour (how to assess behaviour change potential)*", prepared by JLU, summarised behavioural scientific evidence for the potential of changing dietary-related behaviours through behaviour change interventions. It involved a variety of important intervention aspects by answering behaviour change questions, such as: Which behaviours can be changed with which strategies (i.e., what works, compared with what, how well and how long), for whom, in what settings, and why (Michie et al., 2017). The systematic literature review for the umbrella review identified 9,634 papers. After screening, 991 studies were included for full-text review. Based on these, a selection of research evidence for behaviour change strategies tested with the nine target groups of the PLAN'EAT project was presented.

As described above, one of the aims of this deliverable was to gather all results into a meso-analysis report of barriers and enablers influencing food environments and dietary behaviour that should feed into WP4 to develop strategies respectively minimising and maximising their effects. Thus, the survey included questions that would guide the future PLAN'EAT interventions. These questions were based on the findings presented on pp. 19-38 in the IR1 report.

3.1.4 THE NINE LIVING LABS OF THE PLAN'EAT PROJECT

To adopt a participatory and multi-actor approach, PLAN'EAT is implementing most of its activities in 9 living labs (LL), which each targets a specific population group, by creating a citizen panel of 60-200 consumers (see Table 4). The population groups have been selected for their potential for behavioural change, low representativeness in existing studies and statistics, ability to influence other population groups, foreseen impact of interventions, and epidemiological needs. The vulnerability of the study subjects and gender are also considered. The survey was done with target groups, since national level data does not always reflect nuances of target groups¹.

Table 4: PLAN'EAT Living Labs		
Living Lab (LL)	Target group	Setting
France (Auvergne)	Healthy children and adolescents, middle and high socioeconomic status (SES), urban, peri-urban and rural (6-15 years)	School and LL citizen community
Germany (Bavaria)	Obese and overweight children and adolescents from a cohort in Germany (10-18 years)	Clinical
Greece (Attica)	Elderly people, NCDs, all SES (> 60 years)	Free-living population
Hungary (Budapest)	Healthy young adults, low SES (single parents) (20 – 30 years)	Citizen community
Ireland (Dublin)	Healthy young adults – University students, all SES (18-30 years)	University Campus
Italy (Bologna – Pilastro)	Diabetic adults from low SES (low income/ rural/ immigrants), (18-70 years).	Clinical
Poland (Kracow)	Healthy children and adolescents, low SES (1-16 years)	School, kindergarten, and household
Spain (Catalonia)	Healthy adults from middle age to elderly, all SES, (40-85 years)	Citizen community
Sweden	Healthy toddlers, middle and high SES (<6 years)	Pre-school and household

¹ In countries where it proved too difficult to get a large enough sample within the LL, the survey was distributed beyond LL members. This approach recognizes that while national-level data is more widely available and representative, it might not accurately reflect the nuances of specific target groups.

3.2 Method

3.2.1 SURVEY DESIGN

Our assumption posits that the perceived store, restaurant, work, school, and home food environments influences participants' high impact behaviour.

Where possible, we used published scales for the survey. Otherwise, we adapted published scales to the specific behaviour in question, or created new scales based on items from tested scales.

The questionnaire had four overall objectives:

- To measure participants' food intake frequency, namely in relation to the chosen high impact behaviours
- To explore the link between information and education and the high impact behaviours
- To explore possible strategies respectively minimising and maximising the effects of barriers and enablers influencing food environments
- To uncover key dimensions of how food environments affect the chosen high impact behaviours by identifying and analysing the key external and personal dimensions that shape participants' daily perceived experiences with their food environments and finding possible relations with participants' food intake within the high impact behaviours

To do so, the SPG6 survey was structured in eight sections as shown in Table 5 below.

Table 5. SPG6 survey structure		
Theme	Questions	Dimensions
Socio-demographic background	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Please indicate your gender - Please indicate your age (in years) - What is your highest level of education - How would you describe your current employment status? - What is your monthly net household income, i.e. the net income that you (altogether) have after taxes and deductions? - Do you smoke cigarettes (including e-cigarettes etc.)? - How would you describe your level of physical activity? - How would you describe your child's level of physical activity - In general, would you say your health is...: - Do you have any dietary restrictions/preferences? (choose all that apply) 	-
Food frequency questionnaire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In the last month, how many times did you eat or drink the following food items? 	High impact behaviours
Food environments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which of these best describes the neighborhood where you live? - About how long would it take to get from your home to the store where you buy most of your food, if you walked there? - At the store where you buy most of your food, how hard or easy is it to get each of these types of foods? - At the store where you buy most of your food, how would you rate the price of... - Please mark whether you agree or disagree with the following statements for the store where you buy most of your food and your shopping habits at that store. - Please mark whether you agree or disagree with the following statements about the restaurant where you go most often - Is food offered at your daycare/school/university/workplace? 	Availability Accessibility Affordability Accommodation

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do you bring your own food to your daycare/school/university/workplace? 	
Attitudes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In the last 12 months, how often were you concerned about having enough money to eat healthy meals? - In the last 12 months, how often were you concerned about having enough money to eat low environmental impact meals (e.g., organic products or products with low carbon footprint)? - When you shop for food, how important to you is...? - When you eat out at a restaurant or get take-out food, how important to you is...? 	Acceptability Affordability
High impact behavior (specific to the LL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Where would you be most likely to eat/drink XXX? (tick all that apply) - How often is XXX served at your daycare/school/university/workplace? - What would make it more likely for you to eat/drink less/more XXX? (tick all that apply) 	Availability Accommodation
Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From where do you receive information about the <i>health impacts</i> of food? (tick all that apply) - From where do you receive information about the <i>environmental impacts</i> of food? (tick all that apply) 	Information
Education (specific to target groups attending school)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does your university offer...(tick those that apply) 	Availability Accessibility Education

The food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) by Lanfer et al. (2011), which was developed by nutritionists and validated and tested in previous studies, was applied to measure participants' food intake by asking, "In the last month, how many times did you eat or drink the following food items? - Never/ less than once a week, 1-3 times a week, 4-6 times a week, 1 time per day, 2 times per day, 3 times per day, 4 or more times per day" for 61 different food categories.

To measure the food environments, the NEMS-P was applied (Alber et al., 2018), and the five dimensions of food environments (availability, accessibility, affordability, acceptability, and accommodation) (Glanz et al., 2005) were also considered in the questionnaire design.

The Nutrition Education questionnaire developed by The National Center for Education Statistics (National Center for Education Statistics, n.d.) inspired the questions about educational aspects.

This survey was conducted as part of a larger survey that also examined barriers and enablers for dietary behaviours, but individual level. The surveys had a shared part (the demographics and the food frequency questionnaire), and then each their part (this part on food environments and the other part on barriers and enablers for dietary behaviours). The survey items differed slightly between the LLs, since the questions about education were only included for the LLs whose participants attended school or university. Included as Annex D are each of the surveys as shared with the 9 LLs.

Some LLs decided to use a data collection agency and collect data from a convenience sample rather than (solely) their citizen panel. The German LL experienced issues with ethical approval and their citizen panel and was not able to deliver their 100 responses in time to be included in the D2.2 report before its deadline.

In Table 6 below is an overview of each LL's data collection method and process.

Table 6. Data collection process				
Living Lab	Count (after removal of incomplete surveys)	Data collection finalized	Data collection method	Sample type
Sweden	73	15.01.24	Third-party data collection agency	Convenience sample
France	117	15.01.24	Online survey	Citizen panel
Poland	129	08.03.24	Paper survey	Citizen panel
Ireland	104	15.01.24	Online survey	Citizen panel
Hungary	254	15.12.23	Online survey	Citizen panel
Italy	75	21.02.24	Online survey	Citizen panel
Spain	650	27.02.24	Online survey & third-party data collection agency	Citizen panel & convenience sample
Greece	84	14.03.24	Paper survey	Citizen panel
Germany	-	-	-	-
Total	1,487	15.12.23 - 14.03.24	-	

Prior to the launch of the online surveys, the usability and technical functionality of the electronic questionnaire was tested by EUFIC, JLU, and the respective LLs order to check for consistency, layout, and understanding. The online surveys were collected by use of the Qualtrics survey software and either shared via email or a QR-code as an “open survey”, i.e. open for each visitor of the site (Eysenbach, 2004), or in paper-pencil form. For the latter option, the LLs would transfer the responses to SPSS data sheets prepared by JLU.

Questionnaires where the background information, food frequency questionnaire, and/or SPG6 parts were incomplete and/or the survey had been terminated early were removed before analysis.

The IBM SPSS® software was used for the data analysis. Proportions and percentages were used to describe categorical data, while means and standard deviations were used to describe continuous data.

Multiple (three or four) models were fitted to test the effects of the various sets of predictors on each outcome variable (i.e., consumption) with multiple linear regression analyses within each country. The first model tested the effects of *How often is X served at your daycare/school/work; At the store where you buy most of your food, how hard or easy is it to get each of these types of foods?*, and *At the store where you buy most of your food, how would you rate the price of...[multiple food categories]?*. The second model tested *From where does your child receive information about the health impacts of food?*; and *From where does your child receive information about the environmental impacts of food?* as predictors, and finally the effect of *Does your school offer...[multiple answer options]?* was tested in the last model. This was done to avoid issues with multicollinearity that arise when too many related variables are included in the same model. In some countries (Hungary, Spain, Italy), there were many missing values in the predictor *How often is X served your daycare/school/work*. In these cases, *How often is X served your daycare/school/work* was tested in a different model than *At the store where you buy most of your food, how hard or easy is it to get each of these types of foods?*, and *At the store where you buy most of your food, how would you rate the price of...?* to avoid reducing the power of the model.

A summary of the significant relationships of the regression models is shown in Annex E. All results reported are significant at a level of $p < 0.05$.

Ethical considerations

All living labs have taken measures to follow ethical standards and data protection obligations. Each survey participant received clear and understandable written information about the nature, purpose, risks and benefits of their participation in PLAN'EAT, in their local languages. Participants were also provided with a detailed description of the PLAN'EAT project and data management. The participants were informed about the duration of the survey, that their responses would be treated anonymously and confidentially, and that their data would be stored for a minimum of 10 years, that their participation would be voluntary and that it would be possible for them to withdraw at any time from the study, who the investigators were, and the purpose of the study. No personal information was collected or stored, but participants were able to input a personal anonymous code to be able to recollect their data at any time. They were informed that the information they provided could be used anonymously in publications related to the PLAN'EAT project and further scientific publications. Before filling in the survey, participants agreed to the consent form acknowledging that their participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw their consent at any time without giving a reason and without negative consequences. They were informed that their data will be made publicly available in anonymous form on an open data repository. The written information provided and used in each LL can be found in Annex D. The LLs had the opportunity to offer a raffle to participants. The participation in the raffle was voluntary. To take part in the raffle, participants were asked to provide an email address in a separate survey, which was stored separately from participants' survey responses. Ireland and Hungary were the only LLs that offered a raffle, giving participants who completed the survey the option to be entered into a raffle to win a €20/€13.50 voucher respectively.

For LLs that surveyed young children (France, Sweden, Poland), the parents would fill in the survey on behalf of their child. The older children surveyed by the Polish LL (from 12-16 years of age) filled in the paper-pencil survey themselves.

Ethical committee approval was obtained by all living labs previous to the beginning of data collection:

- France: from Clermont Auvergne University, on 23 February 2023, reference number IRB00011540-2022-97
- Hungary: from Local Ethics Committee of the Faculty 09 - Agricultural Sciences, Nutritional Sciences, and Environmental Management, University of Giessen, on 20 November 2023, reference number: 02-2023.
- Greece: from Ethics Committee of Harokopio University, on 2 November 2023, reference number 48 - 02/11/2023
- Poland: from Uniwersytet Jagiellonski W Krakowie, on 5 October 2023, reference number 221.0032.12.2022
- Italy: from Alma Mater Studiorum Universita Di Bologna, Comitato Di Bioetica, on 28 November 2023, reference number 0388072 - 28/12/2023
- Spain: from the Research Ethics Committee of Universitat Oberta de Catalunya on 21 September 2023, reference number CE23-PR27
- Ireland: from University College Dublin, UCD Office of Research Ethics, on 27 November 2023, reference number LS-C-23-227-Gibney
- Sweden: from Erikprövningsmyndigheten, on 1 November 2023, reference number 2023-05798-01

3.3 Results and discussion

3.3.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE SAMPLE

We reached a total of 1,486 respondents, with sample sizes ranging from 75 (Italy) to 650 (Spain). The age ranged from 2 to 92, with Sweden having the lowest mean age of 3 years, while Greece had the highest mean age of 68 years. Spain had a 50/50 gender distribution between females and males, while there were more female respondents in Italy (71%), Greece (65%), France (57%), Ireland (69%), and especially Hungary (99%). Meanwhile, Poland (44%) and Sweden (47%) had a lower share of female participants. The majority of all countries' participants lived in urban neighbourhoods, except for France (Table 7). If not indicated otherwise, the numbers represent the children's data (and not the parents filling in the survey on their behalf).

Country	Italy	Greece	Poland	Sweden	France	Ireland	Hungary	Spain
Count	75	84	129	73	117	104	254	650
Age Mean, (range)	50 (18-80)	68 (60-92)	12 (2-16)	3 (2-7)	10 (2-17)	24 (18-52)	43 (19-59)	52 (22-73)
Age Count, (%)								
0-9	0	0	18 (14%)	73 (100%)	56 (48%)	0	0	0
10-17	0	0	107 (86%)	0	61 (52%)	0	0	0
18-29	8 (11%)	0	0	0	0	97 (93%)	9 (3.5%)	4 (1%)
30-39	20 (27%)	0	3 (14%)	0	0	5 (5%)	45 (18%)	0
40-49	8 (11%)	0	16 (73%)	21 (91%)	0	1 (1%)	163 (64%)	300 (46%)
50-59	8 (11%)	0	3 (14%)	2 (9%)	0	1 (1%)	37 (15%)	260 (40%)
60-69	21 (28%)	51 (60%)	0	0	0	0	0	85 (13)
70-79	8 (11%)	28 (33%)	0	0	0	0	0	1 (0%)
80-99	2 (3%)	5 (6%)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gender Count, (%)	Italy	Greece	Poland	Sweden	France	Ireland	Hungary	Spain
Female	53 (71%)	55 (65%)	57 (44%)	34 (47%)	67 (57%)	72 (69%)	251 (99%)	324 (50%)
Male	22 (29%)	30 (35%)	68 (53%)	39 (53%)	50 (43%)	28 (27%)	3 (1%)	324 (50%)
Other	0	0	3 (2%)	0	0	4 (4%)	0	2 (0%)
Level of education Count, (%)	Italy	Greece	Poland ² (parent)	Sweden (parent)	France (parent)	Ireland	Hungary	Spain
No degree	1 (1%)	1 (1%)	0	0	2 (2%)	1 (1%)	0	0
Primary school degree	2 (3%)	12 (14 %)	2 (4%)	3 (4%)	1 (1%)	0	16 (6%)	46 (7%)
Secondary school degree	21 (28%)	10 (12%)	26 (51%)	31 (43%)	6 (5%)	31 (30%)	70 (28%)	123 (19%)

Vocational school degree	4 (5%)	16 (19%)	11 (22%)	10 (14%)	15 (13%)	0	38 (15%)	175 (27%)
Bachelor's degree	10 (13%)	21 (25%)	5 (10%)	21 (29%)	24 (21%)	31 (30%)	94 (37%)	213 (33%)
Master's degree	35 (47%)	22 (26%)	7 (14%)	7 (10%)	52 (44%)	32 (31%)	32 (13%)	75 (12%)
Doctoral or equivalent level	2 (3%)	2 (2%)	0	1 (1%)	17 (15%)	9 (9%)	4 (2%)	18 (3%)
Employment status	Italy	Greece	Poland ¹ (parent)	Sweden (parent)	France (parent)	Ireland	Hungary	Spain
Full time	42 (56%)	16 (19%)	28 (58%)	53 (73%)	88 (75%)	24 (23%)	183 (72%)	439 (68%)
Part-time	9 (12%)	3 (4%)	12 (25%)	3 (4%)	18 (15%)	25 (24%)	33 (13%)	63 (10%)
Unemployed (looking)	4 (5%)	2 (2%)	1 (2%)	2 (3%)	6 (5%)	2 (2%)	17 (7%)	41 (6%)
Company leave	0	0	2 (4%)	10 (14%)	1 (1%)	0	18 (7%)	9 (1%)
Apprentice /trainee	0	0	1 (2%)	0	0	1 (1%)	0	1 (0%)
Not employed	24 (32%)	64 (75%)	4 (8%)	5 (7%)	4 (3%)	52 (50%)	3 (1%)	96 (15%)
Household net monthly income	Italy	Greece	Poland ¹ (parent)	Sweden (parent)	France (parent)	Ireland	Hungary	Spain
€0-1,500	7 (9%)	4 (5%)	3 (6%)	2 (3%)	1 (1%)	32 (31%)	28 (11%)	36 (6%)
€1,500-3,000	24 (33%)	25 (29%)	33 (64%)	16 (22%)	15 (13%)	42 (40%)	91 (36%)	177 (27%)
> € 3000	41 (57%)	54 (65%)	16 (31%)	55 (75%)	98 (86%)	30 (29%)	135 (53%)	437 (67%)
Neighborhood type	Italy	Greece	Poland	Sweden	France	Ireland	Hungary	Spain
Urban/city or town	62 (83%)	64 (75%)	121 (94%)	41 (56%)	27 (23%)	59 (57%)	152 (60%)	545 (84%)
Suburban	6 (8%)	20 (24%)	6 (5%)	14 (19%)	25 (21%)	37 (36%)	31 (12%)	61 (9%)
Rural	7 (9%)	1 (1%)	2 (2%)	18 (25%)	65 (56%)	8 (8%)	71 (28%)	44 (7%)

¹Poland: Only 51 replies for employment, education, and income, as the remaining respondents (children) were not asked these questions.

The majority of the respondents (63-93%) did not have any dietary restrictions, while flexitarian (3-12%) and vegetarian (0-14%), were the most chosen dietary preferences. Ireland had the highest percentages of flexitarians (12%), vegetarians (14%), and vegans (15%) and the lowest share of dietary restrictions (63%), while Greece had the highest share of participants not following any dietary restrictions (93%), followed by Sweden and France (both 86%). A figure showing the dietary restrictions of the respondents can be found in Annex F.

Results presented per Living Lab

As the subsequent work on the PLAN'EAT project will focus on the LLs separately (such as T2.5: *Synthesis of findings*, D2.5, and WP4 including T4.3.2: *Behavioural change interventions*), the results have been analysed separately and will be presented separately for each of the eight LLs.

3.3.2 POLAND

The Polish LL's target group was healthy children and adolescents of low SES, and of 1-16 years of age, in a school, kindergarten and household setting.

The data were collected via a paper survey and subsequently transferred to IBM SPSS software for analysis. A total of 129 responses were included for analysis. Parents answered on behalf of the younger children below 12 years of age (51 in total), while the rest (12 years or more) answered the survey themselves. The sample had a mean age of 12 years, ranging from 2 to 16 years. 44 % of the sample were female and 53% male. Most of the participants came from an urban city neighbourhood (96%), while 5% came from suburban and 1 % from rural areas.

100% of the participants stated that food was offered at their daycare or school. Nevertheless, 53% said that they often or always brought their own food to daycare/school. 29% would never or rarely bring their own food (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Poland LL food habits

High impact behaviours

The Polish LL chose the following three HIBS, which will be presented separately below:

1. Meat 1 - reduce meat consumption (eat 0-3 portions/week)
2. Legumes – Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)
3. Tap water - Choose tap water instead of bottled water

Meat 1 – reduce meat consumption (eat 0-3 portions/week)

34 % of the children had beef/pork 1-3 times per week, while more had poultry (44-53%) 1-3 times per week (Figure 8).

Figure 7. Poland LL intake of meat. Numbers represent percentages

A total of 80.2% of the participants said that meat was served “sometimes” or “often” at their daycare or school, while 1 out of 10 stated that their daycare/school never served meat (Figure 9). The participants reported that they would be far most likely to eat meat in their own homes (89.1%). Intakes in restaurants/cafes, school/daycare, and friends’/families’ homes were fairly evenly distributed (39.5%, 32.6%, and 30.2%, respectively) (Figure 10).

Figure 8. Poland LL meat served at school/daycare

Figure 9. Poland LL meat food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

Receiving more information about the health and environmental impacts of meat was the most preferred enabler to eat less meat (43.4%), followed by training practical cooking skills (29.5%), and decreased availability of meat (27.1%). Meanwhile, individualized interventions were the least preferred option, selected by only 8.5% (Figure 11).

Figure 10. Poland LL enablers of eating less meat. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Legumes – Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)

About half of the participants had legumes 1-3 times per week (53%), while 15% never had legumes. One out of ten of the participants had legumes once a day (10%) (Figure 12).

Figure 11. Poland LL intake of legumes. Numbers represent percentages.

Two out of three participants stated that legumes were served sometimes or often (67%) at their daycare/school, while one in ten said that they were never served legumes there (11%) (Figure 13).

Figure 12. Poland LL legumes served at daycare/school. Numbers represent percentages

At home and in daycare/school were the places where participants would be most likely to eat legumes (70.5% and 31.0%, respectively). Restaurants/cafes and friends/families' homes were equal, chosen by 14.7% (Figure 14).

Figure 13. Poland LL legumes food environments. Numbers represent percentages.

Same as for meat, receiving more information about the health and environmental effects was the most often chosen enabler (45.7%), but this time followed by knowing that others also ate legumes (31.8%).

Figure 14. Poland LL enablers of eating more legumes. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Tap water – Choose tap water instead of bottled water

64% of the participants drank tap water 1-4 or more times per day, while 8% never drank tap water. For bottled water, there was an interesting U-shaped trend, where 42% of the participants never had bottled water, while at the other end 19% had bottled water 4 or more times a day, suggesting that there could be an either/or preference for choosing bottled water over tap water (Figure 16).

Figure 15. Poland LL intake of tap water. Numbers represent percentages.

55% of the participants were never served tap water at their daycare/school, while just 11% always had it offered (Figure 17).

Figure 16. Poland LL tap water served at daycare/school. Numbers represent percentages.

The participants were more likely to drink tap water at home (61.2%) and at daycare/school (45.7%). Restaurants/cafes were the far least chosen option (5.4%), suggesting that the option of tap water is less available there, or that participants were unlikely to choose that option when dining out (Figure 18).

Figure 17. Poland LL tap water food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Knowing that others also drink tap water and receiving more information about the health and environmental benefits were the two most popular options for drinking more tap water (both 14%). Interestingly, increased availability of tap water was only chosen by 4.7%, suggesting that lack of availability of tap water is not an important barrier to discarding bottled water.

Figure 18. Poland LL enablers of drinking tap water. Numbers represent percentages.

Perception of food environments

The food types that the Polish sample thought were most easy to find where they usually shopped for food were candy and snacks, sugary drinks, and refined grain products (Figure 20). At the other end of the scale, the products that were least available were fresh and frozen fish and unprocessed red meat. If we look at the participants' perceptions of the prices at the same shops, the food categories they think are most expensive are fresh and frozen fish, unprocessed red meat, and nuts. The first three categories were also perceived as least available, as we saw above. The food types that were rated most affordable were refined and whole grain, and fresh and canned/frozen fruits and vegetables (Figure 21).

Poland: At the store where you buy most of your food, how hard or easy is it to get each of these types of foods?

Figure 19. Poland LL perceived availability. Numbers represent percentages

Poland: At the store where you buy most of your food, how would you rate the price of...?

Figure 20. Poland LL perceived prices. Numbers represent percentages.

The statements about their usual food store the Polish participants most agreed with were that the foods near the cash register were mostly unhealthy (3.72), that seasonal fruits and vegetables were easy to find (3.65), and that there were discounts on fruits and vegetables (3.43). The statements least agreed with were that unhealthy foods are placed near the end of aisles (2.54), that they could easily get eco-labelled fish (2.62), and that they often buy the foods near the cash register (2.67) (which were the same ones that most agreed were unhealthy) (Figure 22).

Figure 21. Poland LL shopping experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

Regarding the restaurants where the participants go most often, the statements with the highest agreement were that healthy options cost more (3.24), that healthy options are difficult to find (3.13), and that the restaurants encourage overeating or unhealthy food choices by use of signs and displays (3.06). The statements with the lowest mean agreement were that the restaurant informed about the percentage of organic ingredients (2.45), the environmental impact of the food (2.48), or the origin of the products (2.50), signalling a lack of communication and/or focus on these sustainability aspects from the restaurants' sides.

Figure 22. Poland LL restaurant experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

Information sources

The majority of the participants from Poland received information about health and environment from teachers (63.6 vs. 52.7), social media (58.9 vs. 56.6), and friends/family (57.4 vs. 46.5). The least common sources were podcasts (9.3 vs. 11.6), printed articles (9.3 vs. 10.9) and health professionals (13.2 vs. 10.9) (Figure 24).

Figure 23. Poland LL information sources. Participants were allowed to choose several options. Numbers represent percentages.

Role of education

42.6% of the participants said that their school offered classroom teaching about nutrition and health, and 31.0 % said that their school had many healthy food choices, nutrient information about the food served, and meals corresponding with classroom activities (Figure 25). There seemed to be more focus on health and nutrition than on environment, as e.g. much less said that their schools offered environmentally friendly meals (17.1%).

Figure 24. Poland LL educational offers. Numbers represent percentages. Participant were able to choose several options.

Regression Analysis

There was a significant relationship between how often **tap water** was served at school and the intake of tap water, by which frequency of intake increased for each 1-unit increase (units from 1 to 5, 1=never, 5=always) ($B=0.51, p<0.01$). Interestingly, we found no significant relationship between how often tap water is served at schools and intake of **bottled water** ($B=0.07, p=0.63$).

When participants received their information about health impacts of food from the school curriculum, their frequency of drinking **bottled water** increased by 1.30 ($p=0.03$), and when health information was received

from podcasts, the intake of tap water would increase by 2.20 ($p=0.03$). When they received health information from social media, the frequency of **meat consumption** increased by 0.76 ($p=0.02$).

When participants' school offered environmental information about the food served, their frequency of consuming **legumes** increased by 0.49 ($p=0.01$).

Conclusion

Meat was often served in institutions, but mainly eaten at home. Although unprocessed red meat was perceived as one of the least available and most expensive food categories, decreased meat availability was one the most preferred enablers to reduce its consumption, and increased prices were also mentioned by 1 in 5, suggesting that these could be enhanced even further.

The primary enabler to reduce meat consumption was receiving information about its health and environmental impacts. However, almost half of participants indicated that their school had offered classroom teaching on nutrition and health, and one-third noted that their school had provided nutrient information. This indicates that schools could focus more of this information on the impact of meat, possibly paired with training cooking skills for meat-free meals, as this was the second highest rated enabler. However, receiving health information from social media increased meat consumption frequency, which suggests that the source of information plays a role.

About 15% never consumed legumes, while about 16% ate them daily, showing that some participants were quite far from reaching the target of 3 weekly servings, while some already reached this target. One-third of daycares/schools rarely or never served legumes. One in five thought that increased availability would increase their intake of legumes. Participants were far most likely to eat legumes at home, and only one-third at daycare/school. This suggests that they could benefit from having legumes served more often at their institutions.

Although 43% of participants indicated that their school offered classroom teaching about nutrition and health, the most chosen enabler to increase legume consumption was receiving information about their health and environmental benefits, followed by knowing others consumed legumes, and reduced prices. About forty percent considered legumes somewhat expensive. When participants' school offered environmental information about the food served, their frequency of consuming legumes increased. This suggests that teaching could include more (environmental) information about legumes and that high prices affect their intake.

Almost 70% of the participants were never served tap water at their daycare/school. The participants were most likely to drink tap water at home. The regression analysis showed a positive relationship between how often tap water was served at school and the frequency intake of tap water. Interestingly, we found no significant relationship between how often tap water was served at institutions and intake of bottled water, suggesting that they might be replacing tap water with other types of beverages. Restaurants/cafes were the far least chosen setting for drinking tap water, suggesting that the option of tap water is less available there, and/or that participants were unlikely to choose that option when dining out. Interestingly, increased availability of tap water was only chosen as an enabler by 5%, compared to 14% choosing more information and/or knowing that others drank tap water, suggesting that lack of availability of tap water is not the most important barrier to discarding bottled water. When participants received their health information from podcasts, the intake of tap water would increase substantially, while the intake of bottled water increased when the information came from the school curriculum.

3.3.3 SWEDEN

The Swedish LL's target group was healthy toddlers of households with middle and high socioeconomic status (SES), aged below 6 years, in a preschool and household setting.

The data were collected via a third-party data collection agency and subsequently transferred to IBM SPSS software for analysis. A total of 73 responses were included for analysis. Parents answered the survey on behalf of the children. The children in the sample had a mean age of 3 years, ranging from 2 to 7 years. 47% of the sample were female and 53% male. Most of the participants came from an urban city neighbourhood (56%), while 19% came from suburban and 25% from rural areas.

100% of the Swedish children were offered food at their daycare. And 80.8% would never or rarely bring their own food to kindergarten (Figure 26).

Figure 25. Swedish LL food habits. Numbers represent percentages.

High Impact Behaviours

The Swedish Living Lab focused on the following three high impact behaviours, which will be presented separately below:

1. Meat 4 - Limit the consumption of processed meat (both red and white meat) or even avoid it
2. Legumes – Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)
3. SSB - Drink water instead of sugar-sweetened beverages

Meat 4 - Limit the consumption of processed meat (both red and white meat) or even avoid it

The Swedish children's intake of processed meat is mostly limited, with 53.4% having processed meat, and 45.2% having processed poultry it 1-3 times a week. Only a small percentage consumes it daily, with 4.1-5.5% having it 2 times per day.

Figure 26. Swedish LL consumption of processed meat. Numbers represent percentages

In 27.4% of the cases, the children's daycare would often or always serve processed meat, while almost one in ten (9.6%) would never or rarely serve this type of food (Figure 28). The daycare is the most likely place for almost half the children to eat processed meat (52.1%), only surpassed by their own homes, which was chosen by 71.2% (Figure 29).

Figure 27. Swedish LL processed meat served at daycare. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 28. Swedish LL processed meat food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

Receiving more information about the health and environmental effects of processed meat was considered to be the main enabler of reducing the intake (34.2%), followed closely by decreased availability (31.5%) (Figure 30). About one in four would also need more skills on how to prepare foods without processed meat (23.3%).

Figure 29. Swedish LL enablers of eating processed meat. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Legumes – Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)
41.1% of the children consumed legumes 1-3 times a week. A large number, 39.7%, rarely or never ate legumes.

Figure 30. Swedish LL consumption of legumes. Numbers represent percentages.

Legumes were served sometimes or often in 76.7% of the daycares (Figure 32). This is also the place where the children were most likely to consume legumes, reported by 71.2%, which is more often than in their own (60.3%) or others' homes (23.3%) (Figure 33).

Figure 31. Swedish LL legumes served at daycare. Numbers represent percentages.

Figure 32. Swedish LL legume food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

Increased availability of legumes (35.6%) was considered most influential in increasing legume intake. This availability could be in restaurant settings, since we saw above that only 11% would eat legumes in those places. Receiving more information (32.9%) and reduced prices (31.5%) came close after (Figure 34).

Figure 33. Swedish LL enablers of eating legumes. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose more than one option.

SSB - Drink water instead of sugar-sweetened beverages

For each of the beverages, a wide range of 34.2-86.3% of the children would drink them less than once a week. The most popular beverage to drink 1-3 times per week were uncarbonated sugary drinks and sweetened dairy beverages (both 34.2%). The latter beverage was very popular, being enjoyed once to four times a day by 16.4% of the children. (Figure 35)

Figure 34. Swedish LL consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages. Numbers represent percentages.

20.5% of the children would sometimes or often have sugar-sweetened beverages served at their daycare (Figure 36). This was also the place where 51.1% would be most likely to drinks sugar-sweetened beverages, almost as often as at home (52.1%) (Figure 37).

Figure 35. Swedish LL serving of SSB in daycare. Numbers represent percentages.

Figure 36. Swedish LL sugar-sweetened beverages food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose more options.

Interestingly, decreased availability of these beverages is also the top rated enabler of drinking less sugary beverages (46.6%), which could suggest that making these drinks less available at daycares would be beneficial.

Figure 37. Swedish LL enablers of drinking less SSB. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose more than one option.

Perception of Food Environments

The easiest food items to find in the participants' usual shops are fresh fruits and vegetables, sugary drinks, and candy/snacks. Conversely, fresh fish and plant-based alternatives are less readily available. (Figure 39). Fresh fish is also considered most expensive, whereas dry and canned legumes are considered least expensive (Figure 40).

Sweden: At the store where you buy most of your food, how hard or easy is it to get each of these types of foods?

Figure 38. Swedish LL perceived availability. Numbers represent percentages.

Sweden : At the store where you buy most of your food, how would you rate the price of...?

Figure 39. Swedish LL perceived prices. Numbers represent percentages.

Concerning the food shops that participants would normally go to, the participants mostly agreed that unhealthy foods were often placed near the cash register (3.96) and that seasonal fruits and vegetables were considered easy to find (3.52) (Figure 41).

Figure 40. Swedish LL shopping experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

When asked about the offer at the restaurant that they went to most often, the highest agreement was with the statement that there are many healthy options at the restaurants (3.56), but that they cost more (3.51). There seemed to be a lack of communication or focus from the restaurants' side on information about health and the environment, as these ranked lowest.

Figure 41. Swedish LL restaurant experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

Information Sources

Participants received information about health primarily from friends/family (74.0%) and teachers (49.3%), whereas this was different for information about environmental impacts, which came primarily from friends/family (53.4%), followed by online articles (45.2%) and social media (43.8%).

Figure 42. Swedish LL information sources. Participants were allowed to choose several options. Numbers represent percentages.

Regression analysis

The frequency of daycares serving sugar-sweetened beverages was positively associated with frequency of intake of **sweetened coffee and similar products** ($B=0.33$, $p=0.03$), **sweetened/flavoured milk products** ($B=0.38$, $p=0.03$), **soda drinks** ($B=0.58$, $p<0.01$) and with **sweetened tea or similar beverages** ($B=0.33$, $p=0.02$). Frequency of **soda** intake also increased with availability at local supermarkets ($B=0.48$, $p<0.01$), and with receiving health information from online articles ($B=0.85$, $p=0.03$), and printed articles ($B=1.68$, $p<0.01$).

When participants received information about the health impacts of food from health professionals, this was associated with a -0.69 ($p=0.02$) decreased intake of **sweetened coffee beverages or similar beverages**. Receiving health information from printed articles was associated with an increased frequency of drinking **sweetened/flavoured milk products** ($B=2.30$, $p<0.01$). Receiving information about the environmental effects of food from online articles was associated with decreased frequency of drinking the sweetened/flavoured milk products ($B= -0.70$, $p=0.03$) and a decreased frequency of drinking **sweetened tea or similar beverages** ($B= -0.61$, $p=0.01$). Receiving information about health from teachers was associated with an increased frequency of drinking **sugary non-carbonated drinks** ($B=0.60$, $p=0.04$).

Receiving information about the environmental effects of food from online articles was also negatively associated with consumption frequency of **sweetened coffee or similar beverages** by -0.77 ($p=0.02$).

Frequency of **legume** intake increased by 0.89 when participants received health information from online articles ($p=0.04$).

If health information about food was received from friends/family, the frequency of consuming **processed meat** decreased by -0.70 ($p=0.03$) for **cold cuts** and by -0.72 ($p=0.02$) for **fried poultry**.

Conclusion

All of the Swedish children were offered food at their daycare, and 8 in 10 would never or rarely bring their own food, so their diets can be assumed to be heavily influenced by what is served at their institutions.

The Swedish children's intake of processed meat is mostly limited, with about half having processed meat 1-3 times a week. In about one-fourth of the cases, the children's daycare would often or always serve processed meat, while only about one in ten never or rarely would serve this. The daycare is the most likely place for almost half the children to eat processed meat, only surpassed by their own homes.

For one-third, receiving more information about the health and environmental effects of processed meat was the main enabler of reducing its intake, followed closely by decreased availability, and almost 90% said that processed meat was very or somewhat easy to find in their supermarkets. When health information about food was received from friends/family, the frequency of consuming processed meat decreased, which was also the primary source of both health and environmental information for this target group. This suggests that the knowledge of the children's parents and family has greater influence than that of the daycare personnel.

A large share of the children, almost 40%, rarely or never ate legumes. Legumes were never or rarely served in one-fifth of the daycares, but often/always served in almost 40% of them. The daycares were also the place where the children were most likely to consume legumes, more often than in their own or others' homes. Increased availability was the most often chosen enabler of increasing legume intake, with receiving more information and reduced prices coming close after. The increased availability could be introduced in restaurant settings, since we saw that only one-tenth would be likely to eat legumes there. Meanwhile, more than 90% thought that legumes were easy to find in supermarkets, while over 40% thought they were inexpensive, indicating that the availability and price of legumes could be adjusted elsewhere than only at retailers, e.g. at restaurants and/or daycares.

Twice as many received environmental information from online articles compared to health information. The regression analysis showed that frequency of legume intake increased when participants received health information from online articles.

The most popular of the beverage categories to drink 1-3 times per week were uncarbonated sugary drinks and sweetened dairy beverages. The latter beverage was very popular, being enjoyed once to four times a day by 16% of the children. One-fifth of the children would sometimes or often have sugar-sweetened beverages served at their daycare. This was also the place where half would be most likely to drink sugar-sweetened beverages, almost as often as at home. The frequency of daycares serving sugar-sweetened beverages was positively associated with frequency of a large range of the sugary beverages. Decreased availability of these beverages was also the most chosen enabler of drinking less sugary beverages, which strongly suggests that making these drinks less available at daycares would be beneficial. The regression analysis showed that frequency of soda intake also increased with availability at local supermarkets, where 95% thought that sugary drinks were easy to find.

The type of information sources showed a relationship with the intake of sugar-sweetened beverages. Intake increased with receiving health information from online and/or printed articles, and from teachers. The intake decreased when health information was received from health professionals, or when environmental information came from online articles.

3.3.4 FRANCE

The French LL's target group was (apparently) healthy children and adolescents of middle and high socioeconomic status, aged 6-15 years, in a school setting.

The data were collected via an online survey and subsequently transferred to IBM SPSS software for analysis. A total of 117 responses were included for analysis. The sample had a mean age of 10 years, ranging from 2 to 17 years. 57% of the sample were female and 43% male. 23% of the participants came from urban areas, while 21% came from suburban and 56% from rural areas.

93% of the children were offered food at their schools, and 78.8% would never bring their own food to school (Figure 44).

Figure 43. France LL food habits

High Impact Behaviours

The French Living Lab focused on the following three high impact behaviours, which will be presented separately below:

1. Meat 1 – Reduce meat consumption (eat 0-3 portions/week)
2. Legumes – Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)
3. HFSS – Limit the consumption of ultra-processed food products high in added fat, salt, and sugar

Meat 1 – Reduce meat consumption (eat 0-3 portions/week)

The majority of the French children would have meat 1-3 times per week, ranging from 53.0-75.2% for the different types of meat (Figure 45).

Figure 44. French LL consumption of meat. Numbers represent percentages.

The vast majority of the schools would often or always serve meat (88.5%) (Figure 46), and the children would also be most likely to eat meat at school (78.6%). This was followed by a drop in consumption in their own (59.8%) and others' homes (51.3%) (Figure 47).

Figure 45. French LL meat served at school. Numbers represent percentages.

Figure 46. French LL meat food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

41.9 % of the participants thought that receiving more information about the health and environmental consequences of meat and increasing the availability of alternatives (39.3%) would best enable them to eat less meat. Knowing that others are avoiding meat was the least preferred option (6.0%) (Figure 48).

Figure 47. French LL enablers of consuming less meat. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Legumes – Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)

The majority of the participants (75.2%) would have legumes 1-3 times per week, whereas more than one out of ten had legumes never or less than once a week (12.0%) (Figure 49).

Figure 48. French LL consumption of legumes. Numbers represent percentages.

In 25.9% of the cases, legumes were often or always served at school, while 29.8% never or rarely served these (Figure 50). Less than half as many would eat them at school (41.0%) as they would at home (85.5%) (Figure 51).

Figure 49. French LL legumes served at school. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 50. French LL legumes food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

When asked what would make it more likely for the French children to eat more legumes, most thought that they would need practical skills to prepare and cook them (45.3%). This was followed by increased availability and decreased availability of alternatives, which suggest that an effective enabler would be for e.g. schools to swap or promote legumes for an increased intake (Figure 52).

Figure 51. French LL enablers of legume consumption. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

HFSS – Limit the consumption of ultra-processed food products high in added fat, salt & sugar

The participants' intake of the selected food types varied. Between 23.9% and 56.4% would eat them 1-3 times per week, with chocolate snacks being the most popular option in this category. 19.7% would have biscuits or cakes once a day, whereas more than one out of ten would have sweetened cereals once a day (12.0%) (Figure 53).

Figure 52. French LL consumption of HFSS. Numbers represent percentages.

In 29.8% of the cases, sweet and savoury foods would often or always be served at schools (Figure 54), and about one in four children (26.5%) would be most likely to eat these foods in school (Figure 55). Only 5.8% of the schools would never serve these types of food. Interestingly, friends and family would serve children these foods much more frequently (74.4%) than they would be served at home (32.5%), suggesting that these foods are often served to children visiting friends and family.

Figure 53. French LL HFSS served in school. Numbers represent percentages.

Figure 54. French LL HFSS food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Decreased availability of sweet and savoury foods would help reduce the children's intake of them (53.0%), followed by increased availability of alternatives (38.5%) (Figure 56).

Figure 55. French LL enablers of HFSS consumption. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Perception of Food Environments

Candy/chips, sugary drinks and refined grains were perceived as most accessible, meanwhile plant-based alternatives and fresh and frozen fish were most difficult to find in the participants' usual food store (Figure 57). Fresh fish, unprocessed read meat, and plant-based alternatives were also considered most expensive, while refined grains were cheapest (Figure 58).

France: At the store where you buy most of your food, how hard or easy is it to get each of these types of foods?

Figure 56. French LL perceived availability. Numbers represent percentages.

Figure 57. France LL perceived prices. Numbers represent percentages

When asked about the food store they would most often go to, participants noted that unhealthy foods are frequently found near the cash register (mean score of 4.21) and they least agreed that they bought these foods near the register (1.44). Seasonal fruits and vegetables were perceived as easy to find (3.88), and many stated that they read nutrition labels and information on packaged foods (3.75).

Figure 58. France LL shopping experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

When eating out, there was a high level of agreement about the importance of the ability of making healthy food choices (3.68), but that these options are more expensive (3.50), and that these options are difficult to find (3.28) (Figure 60). The participants disagreed that restaurants would inform about health and environmental impacts.

Figure 59. France LL restaurant experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

Information Sources

Friends/family (74.4% and 79.5%) were the main sources of health and environmental information, whereas social media and podcasts were the least common sources.

Figure 60. France LL information sources. Participants were allowed to choose several options. Numbers represent percentages.

Role of Education

57.3% thought that their schools offered many healthy food choices, while this only accounted for 32.5% when it came to providing environmentally friendly food choices. 23.1% of participants noted that their school provided classroom teaching about nutrition and health, whereas this was much lower for teaching about environmental food choices (5.1%) (Figure 62).

Figure 61. France LL educational offers. Numbers represent percentages. Participant were able to choose several options.

Regression analysis

Schools offering meals corresponding with classroom activities corresponded to an increased intake of **salty snacks like popcorn and crisps** by 0.38 ($p=0.02$). Schools offering information about environmentally sustainable diets in newsletters was associated with an increased frequency of consuming non-homemade **fast-food** ($B=0.49$, $p=0.03$). Attending schools teaching about environmentally sustainable food choices was negatively associated with frequency of consuming **red meat** ($B= -0.85$, $p<0.01$). Classroom teaching about nutrition and health increased intake of **fried red meat** by 0.34 ($p=0.01$). Attending schools offering many environmentally sustainable food choices was associated with a decrease in the consumption of fried red meat by -0.36 ($p<0.01$). Surprisingly, attending schools offering many healthy food choices was associated with increased frequency of consuming **snacks like biscuits and cakes** by 0.75 ($p<0.01$). If the schools supplied environmental information about the food served, it increased the frequency of consuming **chocolate snacks**

($B=0.59$, $p=0.02$) and **savoury snacks** ($B=0.31$, $p=0.04$). If the school offered nutrition information about the food served, this was associated with a 0.38 ($p=0.04$) increase in the frequency of **candy snacks** increased by.

Receiving health information from the school curriculum was associated with increased frequency of consuming **salty snacks like popcorn and crisps** ($B=0.34$, $p=0.03$). When the school curriculum gave environmental information, frequency of consuming **poultry** increased ($B=0.38$, $p=0.01$). Receiving environmental information from commercial communications increased frequency of intake of **chocolate- or nut-based spreads** by 1.44 ($p=0.01$). Intake of **fried red meat** was associated with a decrease of -0.49 ($p<0.01$), when health information came from friends or family. When friends or family were the source of environmental information, this associated with a 0.47 increased intake ($p<0.01$). When the child received environmental information from health professionals, this was associated with a -0.52 decrease in the consumption of **poultry** ($p=0.02$). When the health professionals were the source of health information, frequency of consuming **snacks like biscuits and cakes** increased by 0.83 ($p<0.01$).

Conclusion

93% of the children were offered food at their schools, and almost 80% would never bring their own food to school, so their diets were likely to depend a lot on what was served at their institutions. The vast majority of the schools would often or always serve meat, and the children would also be most likely to eat meat at school. Regression analysis showed that schools offering many environmentally sustainable food choices decrease consumption frequency of fried red meat. About 40% of the participants thought that receiving more information about the health and environmental consequences of meat and and/or increasing the availability of alternatives would enable them to reduce their meat intake. Around 95% found meat easily available at retailers, and 85% found meat both meat and plant-based alternatives expensive, while more than one-fifth found plant-based alternatives difficult to get.

The regression analysis also showed that meat intake would increase when schools offered classroom teaching about health, or when environmental information came from friends or family. Meat intake decreased with schools offering teaching about environmentally sustainable food choices, or when health information came from friends or family. When the school curriculum gave environmental information, frequency of consuming poultry increased. This suggests that schools might recommend meat intake when focusing on healthy diets, or recommending replacing red meat with poultry, when focusing on sustainable diets.

The majority of the participants would have legumes 1-3 times per week, whereas more than one in ten never or rarely would have legumes. In one-fourth of the cases, legumes were often or always served at school, while about one-third never or rarely served these. Less than half as many would eat them at school as they would at home. Only one in four said that their schools offered teaching like cooking classes, and when asked what would make it more likely for the French children to eat more legumes, most thought that they would need practical skills to prepare and cook them, suggesting that they would benefit from more practical teaching about cooking foods such as legumes at school. This was followed by increased availability of legumes and decreased availability of alternatives as enablers, and more than 85% said that legumes were easily available at retailers, which suggest that an effective enabler for an increased intake would be, for example, for schools to swap or promote legumes. The regression analysis showed no significant results for legumes.

The participants' intake of the HFSS food types varied. About one in five would have biscuits or cakes once a day, and about one out of ten would have sweetened cereals once a day. In about a third of the cases, sweet and savoury foods would often or always be served at schools, and about one in four children would be most likely to eat these foods in school. Only about 6% of the schools would never serve these types of food. Interestingly, the children would be more likely to consume these foods at friends/families' homes than they would at home, suggesting that these foods are often served to children visiting. Decreased availability of sweet and savoury foods were perceived to be an enabler of reducing the children's intake of them, followed by increased availability of alternatives; meanwhile, candy and snacks were viewed as less expensive than, for example, fruits and vegetables, and more easily available than for example, nuts.

Intake of HFSS foods increased with schools offering meals corresponding with classroom activities, information about environmentally sustainable diets in newsletters, many healthy food choices, and environmental and/or nutrition information about the food served. Intake also increased with receiving health information from the school curriculum or health professionals, or receiving environmental information from commercial communications. These findings are interesting and could point towards the education or information environments being less effective means of reducing the children's intake of HFSS.

3.4.2. HUNGARY

The Hungarian LL's target group was healthy young adults (single parents) of low SES, aged 20-30 years, in a community setting.

The data were collected via an online survey and subsequently transferred to IBM SPSS software for analysis. A total of 254 responses were included for analysis. The sample had a mean age of 43 years, ranging from 19 to 59 years. The vast majority (99%) of the sample were female. Most of the participants came from urban areas (60%), while 12% came from suburban and 28% from rural areas. Only 15% said that food was offered at their school or workplace, and 61% would often or always bring their own food with them to their school or workplace (Figure 63).

Figure 62. Hungary LL food habits

High Impact Behaviours

The Hungarian Living Lab focused on the following three high impact behaviours, which will be presented separately below:

1. Meat 3 - Choose plant-based alternatives instead of meat as an alternative source of protein (twice a week)
2. Meat 5 - Limit the consumption of red meat or even avoid it
3. F&V – Eat 5 servings of vegetables and fruits per day

Meat 3 - Choose plant-based alternatives instead of meat as an alternative source of protein (twice a week)

87.8% of the participants consumed plant-based alternatives never or less than once a week (Figure 64). In 52.7% of the cases, schools/workplaces would never or rarely serve plant-based alternatives (Figure 65), and 83.1% of the participants said they were most likely to consume plant-based alternatives at home (Figure 66).

Figure 63. Hungary LL consumption of plant-based alternatives. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 64. Hungary LL plant-based alternatives served at school/work. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 65. Hungary LL plant-based alternatives food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

Reduced availability of alternatives (such as meat) was considered to be the strongest enabler, chosen by 83.3% of the participants, followed by reduced prices (63.4%) and increased availability (33.1%) (Figure 67). Knowing that others are also choosing plant-based alternatives would only motivate 2%.

Figure 66. Hungary LL enablers of consuming plant-based alternatives. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Meat 5 - Limit the consumption of red meat or even avoid it

59.8-64.6% of the Hungarian participants never consumed red meat, or consumed it less than once a week (Figure 68). To 34.2%, red meat would often or always be served at their school or workplace, and the majority would be most likely to eat red meat at home (57.9%) or restaurants/cafes (29.9%) (Figure 69).

Figure 67. Hungary LL consumption of red meat. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 68. Hungary LL red meat served at school/workplace. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 69. Hungary LL red meat food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

To reduce their intake of red meat, participants considered that receiving more information about the health and environmental effects (24.0%), followed by their decreased availability (21.7%), and increased availability of alternatives (20.9%) would be the most promising enablers (Figure 71).

Figure 70. Hungary LL enablers of consuming red meat. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

F&V – Eat 5 servings of vegetables and fruits per day

17.7-24.4% of the participants never had vegetables (raw or cooked) or fresh fruits, or had them less than once a week. Only 26.8% would eat fruit once or more every day (Figure 72). 39.5% of the participants' schools or workplaces would rarely or never serve fruit and vegetables (Figure 73). The vast majority would also be most likely to eat these types of food at home (87.8%). Only 13.0% would eat fruits and vegetables at restaurants or cafes (Figure 74).

Figure 71. Hungary LL consumption of F&V. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 72. Hungary LL F&V served at school. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 73. Hungary LL F&V food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

76.0% agreed that reducing the costs of fruit and vegetables would help them to increase their intake of these healthy foods (Figure 75). This enabler was three times as popular as the second choice, which was increased availability (25.6%).

Figure 74. Hungary LL enablers of consuming F&V. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Perception of Food Environments

The availability of candy/crisps and sugary drinks was seen as very high, while fresh fish and plant-based alternatives were particularly difficult to find, highlighting challenges in accessing diverse protein sources (Figure 76). Fresh fish and plant-based alternatives were also seen as very expensive (Figure 77).

Figure 75. Hungary LL perceived availability. Numbers represent percentages

Hungary: At the store where you buy most of your food, how would you rate the price of...?

Figure 76. Hungary LL perceived prices. Numbers represent percentages

Participants commonly agreed that it was easy to find fruits and vegetables at their supermarket (3.90) and that these foods are promoted with discounts (3.48), but that many signs and displays also promoted unhealthy foods (3.17) (Figure 78). Due to an unfortunate error in the Qualtrics online survey script, the item “It’s easy to find plant-based alternatives (plant-based milk, vegan/vegetarian burgers, plant-based meat, etc.)” was not included as an answer option to the question about shopping experiences for this target group.

Figure 77. Hungary LL shopping experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

Although many agreed that it was important to them to be able to eat healthily at restaurants (3.33) they found that healthy options at restaurants are more expensive (3.83) and difficult to find (3.26), and they mainly disagreed that vegan/vegetarian menus were easy to find at restaurants (2.74) (Figure 79).

Figure 78. Hungary LL restaurant experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

Information Sources

Online articles (63.0% and 68.5%) and social media (49.6% and 54.3%) were the main sources of health and environmental information. University curriculum was the least common source (3.9% and 2.8%). 24.4% would receive information about health from friends and family, but no one would hear about environmental impacts from this source.

Figure 79. Hungary LL information sources. Participants were allowed to choose several options. Numbers represent percentages

Regression analysis

Frequency of consuming **cooked vegetables**: a) decreased in those who received health information from commercial communications ($B = -0.64, p < 0.01$), b) increased when health information was received from health professionals ($B = 0.32, p = 0.05$), and c) increased in those who received environmental information from commercial communications ($B = 0.56, p = 0.02$). Consumption of **raw vegetables** decreased ($B = -0.84, p < 0.01$) for those who received health information from commercial communications and increased when schools offered many environmentally friendly food choices ($B = 4.00, p = 0.01$). **Fresh fruit** consumption frequency increased in those who received health information came from health professionals ($B = 0.46, p = 0.03$) and in those who received environmental information from podcasts ($B = 0.61, p = 0.01$).

Intake of **plant-based proteins** was more frequent when health information came from the university curriculum ($B = 0.46, p = 0.02$), and from online articles ($B = 0.19, p = 0.04$).

When health information came from the university curriculum, frequency of **red meat** intake increased by 0.60 ($p = 0.03$).

Conclusion

There was room for increasing the intake of plant-based alternatives, as the majority of the participants consumed these never or less than once a week. For half, schools/workplaces would never or rarely serve plant-based alternatives, and about 80% of the participants said they were most likely to consume plant-based alternatives at home. Reduced availability of alternatives (such as meat) was the strongest enabler, followed by reduced prices and increased availability. However, the participants thought that plant-based alternatives were particularly difficult to find and very expensive, and mainly disagreed that vegan/vegetarian menus are easy to find at restaurants. This highlights challenges in accessing and affording these diverse

protein sources, and that schools and workplaces could effectively increase their offering of these types of food.

Due to an unfortunate error in the Qualtrics online survey script, the item “It’s easy to find plant-based alternatives (plant-based milk, vegan/vegetarian burgers, plant-based meat, etc.)” was not included as an answer option to the question about shopping experiences to this target group, and the response rate to the education question was very low. However, the regression analysis showed that an intake of plant-based proteins was slightly more frequent when health information came from the university curriculum and from online articles – the latter being the main source of both health and environmental information for the participants.

The participants had a low to moderate intake of red meat. Red meat would often or always be served at one-third of schools or workplaces, and the majority would be most likely to eat red meat at home or at restaurants/cafes, making the latter two environments possible areas of focus.

Participants thought that the most effective enablers of reducing red meat intake was to receive more information about the health and environmental effects, followed by their decreased availability, and increased availability of alternatives. Meanwhile, fresh fish and plant-based alternatives were perceived to be highly unavailable at retailers, and almost 40% thought that unprocessed red meat was very expensive, but not as expensive as fresh fish and plant-based alternatives, which highlights the challenges in accessing alternative protein sources. The participants also agreed that red meat was often discounted or promoted at retailers, while they disagreed that plant-based menus were easy to find at restaurants and agreed that healthy options at restaurants were more expensive. The regression analysis showed that when health information came from the university curriculum (which was the least common source for both health and environmental information), the frequency of red meat intake increased, which could indicate that universities might be recommending meat as part of a healthy diet.

The participants had a rather low intake of fruits and vegetables, as about a fifth of the participants never had them, or had them less than once a week, and only one-fourth would eat fruit once or more daily. About 40% of the participants’ schools or workplaces would rarely or never serve fruit and vegetables. The vast majority would also be most likely to eat these types of food at home. The majority agreed that reducing the costs of fruit and vegetables would help them to increase their intake frequency. This enabler was three times as popular as the second choice, which was increased availability. This is underscored by results showing that more than 9 out of 10 found fresh and canned/frozen fruits and vegetables easily accessible at supermarkets, but more than 7 out of 10 found them somewhat or very expensive. Further to this point, participants highly agreed that it was easy to find fruits and vegetables at their supermarket, and that these foods are promoted with discounts, but that many signs and displays were also promoting unhealthy foods. Although many agreed that it was important to them to be able to eat healthily at restaurants, they found healthy options at restaurants to be more expensive, and that healthy fruit and vegetable options were difficult to find. Only about one tenth would eat fruits and vegetables at restaurants or cafes. Frequency of consuming both raw and cooked vegetables decreased with receiving health information from commercial communication, suggesting that these might be promoting other types of food. Conversely, intake frequency of vegetables increased when health information came from health professionals, when environmental information came from commercial communications, and when schools offered many environmentally friendly food choices – the latter might be linked to increased availability. Fresh fruit consumption frequency increased when health information came from health professionals and when environmental information came from podcasts. There seems to be a positive effect between health professionals giving advice and overall fruit and vegetable intake.

If interpreting the results for a wider population, it is worth noting that the sample was 99% female.

3.4.3. IRELAND

The Irish LL's target group was healthy young adults (university students) of all SES, aged 18-30 years, in a university campus setting.

The data was collected via an online survey and subsequently transferred to IBM SPSS software for analysis. A total of 104 responses were included for analysis. The sample had a mean age of 24 years, ranging from 18 to 52 years. 69% of the sample were female and 27% male. Most of the participants came from urban (57%) or suburban (35%) areas, while 8% were from rural areas.

In 96% of the cases, the universities offered food. Nevertheless, 71.1% of the participants would often or always bring their own food (Figure 82).

Figure 80. Ireland LL food habits. Numbers represent percentages

High Impact Behaviours

The Irish Living Lab focused on the following five high impact behaviours, which will be presented separately below:

1. Meat 1 – Reduce meat consumption (eat 0-3 portions/week)
2. F&V – Eat 5 servings of vegetables and fruits per day
3. Legumes – Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)
4. HFSS – Limit the consumption of ultra-processed food products high in fat, salt, and sugar
5. Energy needs - Know your energy (caloric) needs and eat accordingly (don't over-/under-eat)

Meat 1 – Reduce meat consumption (eat 0-3 portions/week)

26.0-52.9% of the sample would eat one of the four types of meat 1-3 times per week, while 30.8-73.1% would eat it more rarely or never (Figure 83).

Figure 81. Ireland LL consumption of meat. Numbers represent percentages

Meat was often or always served at the universities in 82.0% of the cases (Figure 84), and this is also where 28.8% of the participants would be most likely to eat meat (Figure 85). Even more would eat meat at home (61.5%), or at friends/families homes (38.5%).

Figure 82. Ireland LL meat served at school. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 83. Ireland LL meat food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

Decreased availability of meat (41.3%), together with increased availability of their alternatives (37.5%) and increased prices (38.5%) were the most often chosen enablers for reducing meat intake (Figure 86).

Figure 84. Ireland LL enablers of consuming meat. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

F&V – Eat 5 servings of vegetables and fruits per day

9.6-20.2% of the participants had vegetables (cooked or raw) and/or fresh fruit 2 times a day, while 4.8-7.7% never or rarely had one of these types of food (Figure 87).

Figure 85. Ireland LL consumption of F&V. Numbers represent percentages

Fruits and vegetables were often or always served at 51.0 of the schools, while 15.4% never or rarely served them (Figure 88). Schools were also the place where 32.7% of the participants were most likely to eat fruits and vegetables, but this number was almost three times higher for their own homes (98.1%) (Figure 89).

Figure 86. Ireland LL meat served at school. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 87. Ireland LL F&V food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

In order to increase their intake of these healthy foods, the majority of the participants (73.1%) thought that reduced prices would be most effective, followed closely by increased availability (70.2%) (Figure 90).

Figure 88. Ireland LL enablers of consuming F&V. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Legumes – Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)

A quarter of the participants would rarely or never eat legumes at all, while almost half (48.1%) would eat them 1-3 times per week (Figure 91).

Figure 89. Ireland LL consumption of legumes. Numbers represent percentages

At 34.% of the schools, legumes would rarely or never be served, while they were often or always on the menu at 18.2% of the schools (Figure 92). The schools were also the least likely place for the participants to eat legumes (13.5%), while homes was by far the most likely place, chosen by 79.8% (Figure 93).

Figure 90. Ireland LL legumes served at school. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 91. Ireland LL legumes food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

Increased availability would make it more likely for 57.7% of the participants to eat more legumes, and 39.4% would also like to have more practical cooking skills to prepare legumes (Figure 94).

Figure 92. Ireland LL enablers of consuming legumes. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

HFSS – Limit the consumption of ultra-processed food products high in fat, salt & sugar

Intake of the different types of foods high in fat, salt or sugar varied. 19.2-39.4% of the participants would eat them 1-3 times per week, with snacks like chocolate and chocolate bars being the most popular type (Figure 95).

Figure 93. Ireland LL consumption of HFSS. Numbers represent percentages

Sweet and savoury foods high in salt, sugar and/or fat would often or always be served at 71% of the universities (Figure 96). Only 5% would rarely or never serve them. 36.5% of the participants were also most likely to eat these foods at their universities. Friends/families homes and cafes/restaurants were the most likely places to eat these foods, suggesting that they are popular options to serve and eat when eating out (Figure 97).

Figure 94. Ireland LL HFSS served at school. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 95. Ireland LL HFSS food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

Availability was a big theme in reducing the intake of sweet and savoury foods, with decreased availability of these types of food, and increased availability of alternatives being the two enablers that more than half of the sample selected (58.7% and 51.0%) (Figure 98).

Figure 96. Ireland LL enablers of consuming HFSS. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Energy needs - Know your energy (caloric) needs and eat accordingly (don't over-/under-eat)

Participants would be most likely to consider their energy needs when eating at home (70.2%), while only about one in ten (12.5%) would consider them when eating out. 4.8% never considered their energy needs (Figure 99).

Figure 97. Ireland LL energy needs food environments. Numbers represent percentages.

Perception of food environments

The unhealthier options were perceived as most available at the participants' local supermarkets, with sweets/crisps, processed meat, sugar drinks, and refined grains being the most easily available types of food (Figure 100). Fresh and frozen fish were most difficult to find. Refined grains were also cheapest, followed by canned legumes and canned/frozen fruits and vegetables (Figure 101). Participants thought that fresh fish and plant-based alternatives were the most expensive foods.

Figure 98. Ireland LL perceived availability. Numbers represent percentages

Ireland: At the store where you buy most of your food, how would you rate the price of...?

Figure 99. Ireland LL perceived prices. Numbers represent percentages

Regarding the participants' local supermarkets, most agreed that the supermarkets promote unhealthy foods by placing them at the cash register (3.96), at the end of the aisles (3.39%), or by encouraging their sales by use of signs and displays (3.22) (Figure 102). Due to an unfortunate error in the Qualtrics online survey script, the item "It's easy to find plant-based alternatives (plant-based milk, vegan/vegetarian burgers, plant-based meat, etc.)" was not included as an answer option to the question about shopping experiences for this target group.

Figure 100. Ireland LL shopping experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

Eating healthily at restaurants was a big priority (3.34), although many agreed that the healthy options were more expensive (3.13). Respondents had the same level of agreement for the statement that restaurants they most often frequented offered many healthy options and that healthy options are hard to find (both 3.03) (Figure 103).

Figure 101. Ireland LL restaurant experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

Information sources

Social media (68.3%) and online articles (57.7%) were the most common sources of information about the environmental impact of food, while social media (64.4%) was followed by health professionals (46.2%) as the main sources of health information. None of the participants would receive information about the environmental impacts from friends and family, while 26.9% would receive information about the health impacts from these (Figure 104).

Figure 102. Ireland LL information sources. Participants were allowed to choose several options. Numbers represent percentages

Role of Education

57.7% of the participants stated that their universities offered many healthy food choices, while less environmentally friendly food choices were on the menu (19.2%). The schools would also focus on communicating the nutritional aspects of the food served (29.8%), rather than the environmental aspects (3.8%) (Figure 105).

Figure 103. Ireland LL educational offers. Numbers represent percentages. Participant were able to choose several options.

Regression analysis

Schools offering nutrient information about the foods served was associated with reduced frequency of consuming **snacks like biscuits and cakes** ($B = -1.30, p = 0.02$). Those who received environmental information from online articles ($B = 0.61, p = 0.04$) more frequently consumed **chocolate snacks**. But those who received environmental information from printed articles had less frequent consumption of such snack ($B = -0.76, p = 0.03$), it would decrease. Frequency intake of **candy snacks** also decreased when printed articles was the environmental information source ($B = -0.49, p = 0.04$). When health communication came from commercial communications, this was associated with a less frequent intake of **salty snacks** ($B = -0.48, p = 0.04$). However when schools offered many healthy food choices, this was associated with increased intake of salty snacks ($B = 0.42, p = 0.02$). **Snack bar** consumption was more frequent when environmental information came from the school curriculum ($B = 0.69, p = 0.02$) and when schools offered many healthy food choices ($B = 0.32, p = 0.04$). The frequency of consuming **chocolate- or nut-based spreads** increased by 1.14 ($p < 0.01$) when health information came from the school curriculum, and by 0.66 ($p = 0.03$) when it came from social media.

The frequency of eating **fast-food** increased with each 1-unit increase in the frequency of universities serving sweets and crisps (units from 1 to 5, 1=never, 5=always) ($B = 0.77, p < 0.01$). More frequent consumption of fast-food ($B = 0.97, p < 0.01$) and **snacks like biscuits and cakes** ($B = 1.40, p = 0.02$) was associated with schools offering nutrient information in newsletters. On the other hand the provision of environmental information was association with reduced frequency of consuming **chocolate snacks** ($B = -1.35, p = 0.03$). Surprisingly, the less available sweets and crisps were at the supermarket, the higher the frequency intake of **snacks like biscuits and cakes was** ($B = 0.87, p = 0.049$).

The frequency of eating **cooked vegetables** decreased for each 1-unit increase in the perceived expensiveness of canned/frozen fruits and vegetables in local supermarkets (units from 1 to 4, 1=very inexpensive, 4=very expensive) ($B = -0.52, p = 0.02$). The frequency of eating **legumes** decreased for each 1-unit increase in the perceived expensiveness of dry/canned legumes in local supermarkets ($B = -0.49, p < 0.01$). Legume intake also decreased when environmental information came from social media ($B = -0.65, p = 0.01$). **Fresh fruit** was consumed more frequently when health information came from the university curriculum ($B = 1.64, p < 0.01$), and decreased when health information came from online articles ($B = -1.09, p < 0.01$).

Perceived lack of availability of processed red meat in the participants' local supermarkets, was linked to less frequent consumption of **processed poultry** ($B = -0.37, p = 0.02$) (processed white meat was not measured). When social media was the source of health information, **red meat** ($B = 0.63, p = 0.03$) and processed poultry ($B = 0.33, p < 0.01$) was consumed more frequently, and in the case of environmental information, social media as a source was linked to increased **poultry** intake ($B = 0.45, p = 0.04$). If commercial communications were the health information source, poultry intake was more frequent ($B = 0.61, p = 0.01$), and if commercial communications were a source of environmental information, processed poultry consumption was less frequent ($B = -0.36, p = 0.01$).

Conclusion

Decreased availability of meat, together with increased availability of their alternatives and increased prices were the most chosen enablers for reducing meat intake, supported by the regression analysis showing that perceived lack of availability of processed red meat in the participants' local supermarkets was linked to less frequent consumption of processed poultry. However, 100% of the participants thought that processed red meat was easy to find at retailers. Further, fresh fish and plant-based alternatives were the most expensive foods. This indicated that the high availability of meat and high costs of their alternatives might be affecting participants' meat intake negatively. Meat was often or always served at the universities in 8 out of 10 the cases, and this is also where more than a quarter of the participants would be most likely to eat meat, while even more would eat meat at home or at friends/families homes, which suggests that universities and retailers/homes were the primary environments of focus concerning meat intake.

Frequency of red meat and poultry consumption increased when social media was the source of health or environmental information, or when commercial communications were the health information source, which suggests that these sources might be promoting meat. Conversely, if commercial communications were a source of *environmental* information, processed poultry consumption frequency decreased, which could be due to this source promoting a lower meat intake for environmental reasons.

Fruits and vegetables were often or always served at only half of the schools, while about 15% never or rarely served them. Schools were also the place where one-third of the participants were most likely to eat fruits and vegetables, but this number was almost three times higher for their own homes. In order to increase their intake of these healthy foods, the vast majority of the participants thought that reduced prices would be most effective, followed closely by increased availability. More than 9 out of 10 thought that fresh and canned/frozen fruits and vegetables were easily available at retailers and they agreed that seasonal fruits and vegetables were easy to find. However, 6 in 10 thought fresh fruits and vegetables were expensive - although there was a mean agreement that they were often discounted or promoted. The regression analysis also showed that the frequency of eating cooked vegetables decreased for each 1-unit increase in perceived expensiveness of canned/frozen fruits and vegetables in local supermarkets. Participants disagreed that restaurants offered healthy fruit and vegetable options. These findings highlight the impact and opportunities that affordability and availability, namely at schools and retailers, have for the participants' intake of fruit and vegetables.

Further, fresh fruit consumption frequency increased when health information came from the university curriculum and decreased when health information came from online articles, suggesting that universities focusing on health information might also offer more fresh fruit options or promote fruit intake.

The participants' intake of legumes showed room for improvement, as a quarter of the participants would rarely or never eat legumes at all, while almost half would eat them 1-3 times per week. More than 9 out of 10 found them easily available at retailers, and 8 in 10 thought they were inexpensive. At one-third of the schools, legumes would rarely or never be served. The schools were also the least likely place for the participants to eat legumes, while homes were by far the most likely place, showing an opportunity to introduce more legumes at schools, not least considering that increased availability would make it more likely for over half of the participants to eat more legumes. This was followed by practical cooking skills to prepare legumes, and by reduced prices. Frequency of eating legumes decreased with perceived expensiveness of dry/canned legumes in local supermarkets. The frequency also decreased when environmental information came from social media, which could be due to a lack of focus on these types of alternative proteins.

Availability was a big theme in reducing the intake of sweet and savoury foods, with decreased availability of these types of food, and increased availability of alternatives each chosen by more than half of the participants. Sweet and savoury foods high in salt, sugar and/or fat would often or always be served at the majority of the universities. Only 5% would rarely or never serve them. More than one-third of the participants were also most likely to eat these foods at their universities. The regression analysis showed that the intake frequency of some HFSS increased with frequency of universities serving sweets and crisps. Meanwhile, friends/families homes and cafes/restaurants were the most likely places to eat these foods, suggesting that these foods are popular options to serve and eat when eating out.

The unhealthier options were perceived as most available at the participants' local supermarkets, with sweets/crisps, processed meat, sugar drinks, and refined grains being the most easily available types of food. Most agreed that the supermarkets promote unhealthy foods by placing them at the cash register or end of the aisles or by encouraging their sales by use of signs and displays. Interestingly, the less available sweets and crisps were at the supermarket, the higher the frequency intake of snacks like biscuits and cakes was, which could be due to those foods primarily being bought or consumed elsewhere.

Surprisingly, some HFSS intake increased when schools offered many healthy food choices and/or nutrient information in newsletters, which needs further investigation to explain. Intake frequency decreased when environmental information came from online articles or the school curriculum, or when health information came from the school curriculum or from social media, suggesting that these sources did not focus on HFSS

foods. Intake frequency of HFSS decreased when schools offered nutrient information about the foods served (suggesting that this might be effective in guiding food choices at schools), when environmental information came from printed articles, or when health information came from commercial communications.

The majority of the participants would be most likely to consider their energy needs when eating at home, while only about one in ten would consider them when eating out, where the average agreement was that restaurants do not provide nutrition information such as calorie content. The participants on average agreed that they did read nutrition labels at supermarkets, though 5% never would never consider their energy needs. Almost one third said that their schools provided nutrient information about the food served. These results suggest that more schools and restaurants could provide nutrient information.

3.4.4. SPAIN

The Spanish LL's target group was healthy adults from middle age to elderly of all SES, aged 40-85 years, in a community setting.

The data were collected partly via an online survey and partly via a third-party data collection agency, and subsequently transferred to IBM SPSS software for analysis. A total of 650 responses were included for analysis. The sample had a mean age of 52 years, ranging from 22 to 73 years. The gender distribution was balanced with 50% female and 50% male. Most of the participants came from urban areas (84%), while 9% came from suburban and 7% from rural areas.

Food was only offered at 24% of the participants' workplaces. 43.3% of the participants would often or always bring their own food to work suggesting that a portion of the participants would purchase food outside work to eat during the day (Figure 106).

Figure 104. Spain LL food habits. Numbers represent percentages.

High Impact Behaviours

The Spanish Living Lab focused on the following three high impact behaviours, which will be presented separately below:

1. Meat 5 - Limit the consumption of red meat or even avoid it
2. F&V – Eat 5 servings of vegetables and fruits per day
3. Legumes – Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)

Meat 5 - Limit the consumption of red meat or even avoid it

Red meat consumption is relatively low, with 32.3-44.6% never or rarely eating one of the two types of red meat. Meanwhile, 43.5-49.5% eat them 1-3 times per week (Figure 107).

Figure 105. Spain LL consumption of red meat. Numbers represent percentages

As much as 68.3% of the workplaces would never or rarely serve red meat, but part of this could be explained by the low number of workplaces serving food (Figure 108). However, 86.5% of the participants said that they would be most likely to eat red meat at work (Figure 109). This could be explained by participants buying lunch with red meat from outside work to bring to their workplace, or by participants choosing the red meat options on the rare occasions they are served at work.

Figure 106. Spain LL red meat served at work. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 107. Spain LL red meat food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

Increased prices (32.8%), decreased availability and more information about the health and environmental effects (both 26.3%) were the highest rated enabling factors that participants thought would decrease their red meat intake (Figure 110).

Figure 108. Spain LL enablers of consuming red meat. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

F&V – Eat 5 servings of vegetables and fruits per day

Spain showed a relatively high intake of fruits and vegetables, with about one in four (22.3-26.6%) having one of the three types of food 4.6 times per week, and 18.5% having fresh fruit 2 times per day (Figure 111). 5.5-13.1% would never or rarely eat one of the types of fruits/vegetables measured.

Figure 109. Spain LL consumption of F&V. Numbers represent percentages

55.8% of the workplaces would never serve fruit and vegetables, which again in part could be explained by the low number of workplaces serving food (Figure 112). However, 24.1% would of workplaces would often or always serve fruits and vegetables. The vast majority of the participants were most likely to eat fruits and vegetables at home (90.2%) (Figure 113).

Figure 110. Spain LL F&V served at work. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 111. Spain LL F&V food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

The Spanish participants would prefer reduced prices (58.6%) on fruits and vegetables to facilitate an increased intake of those foods, while they would also like them to become more available (36.0%) (Figure 114).

Figure 112. Spain LL enablers of consuming F&V. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Legumes – Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)

Most of the Spanish participants had legumes 1-3 times per week (73.4%), while about one in ten would never eat this type of food (Figure 115).

Figure 113. Spain LL consumption of legumes. Numbers represent percentages

59.8% of the workplaces never served legumes, which once again in part could be explained by the low number of workplaces serving food (Figure 116). Most of the participants would also mainly eat legumes at home (94.0%), while only 14.0% would eat legumes at work (Figure 117).

Figure 114. Spain LL F&V served at work. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 115. Spain LL F&V food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

Reduced prices (34.6%) and practical skills training (31.2%) would enable participants to eat more legumes, the latter suggesting that they lack the necessary cooking skills to prepare these plant-based proteins (Figure 118).

Figure 116. Spain LL enablers of consuming F&V. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Perception of food environments

Fresh fish and plant-based protein were among the least available food types at the participants' local supermarkets, suggesting difficulties in purchasing these alternatives to meat (Figure 119). These two food

types were also seen as being most expensive (Figure 120). Sweets/crisps, refined grains, and legumes were rated most affordable. The latter is an interesting finding, as reduced prices on legumes was also the highest rated enabler above.

Figure 117. Spain LL perceived availability. Numbers represent percentages

Spain: At the store where you buy most of your food, how would you rate the price of...?

Figure 118. Spain LL perceived prices. Numbers represent percentages

There was a high level of agreement with the statement that fruits and vegetables were easy to find in the local food shops (3.79), while unhealthy options are also promoted by placement (3.75) and signs (3.18). The participants also sought out nutritional information themselves (3.34), showing a level of interest or responsibility (Figure 121).

Figure 119. Spain LL shopping experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

The participants valued health highly when eating out (3.52) and felt that there were many healthy menu options available (3.17), although they tended to be more expensive (3.41) (Figure 122). There was little agreement that restaurants communicated openly about health and environmental aspects.

Figure 120. Spain LL restaurant experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

Information sources

Health professionals were the most common source of information about health impacts of food (48.0%), and interestingly also to some extent of information about the environmental impacts (23.5%) (Figure 123). Friends and family were only a source of information for health, not environmental impacts (28.2%). Social media and online articles were popular sources for both types of information.

Figure 121. Spain LL information sources. Participants were allowed to choose several options. Numbers represent percentages.

Regression Analysis

The intake of **cooked vegetables** was more frequent when podcasts were the source of environmental information ($B=0.34$, $p=0.04$). **Fresh fruit** intake frequency decreased per 1-unit increment of perceived expensiveness of canned/frozen fruits and vegetables sold at local supermarkets (units from 1 to 4, 1=very inexpensive, 4=very expensive) ($B= -0.24$, $p=0.03$), whereas the frequency increased with perceived expensiveness of fresh fruits and vegetables ($B=0.29$, $p<0.01$). The intake also increased when podcasts ($B=0.52$, $p=0.03$), printed articles ($B=0.37$, $p=0.02$), or health professionals ($B=0.59$, $p<0.01$) were the sources of health information. Frequency of having fruits and vegetables served at school/workplace was positively associated with frequency of **raw vegetable** intake ($B=0.94$, $p<0.01$). Online articles as a source of health information ($B=0.23$, $p=0.03$) and university lecturers as a source of environmental information ($B=0.46$, $p<0.01$) were both positively associated with a more frequent intake of raw vegetables.

Legume intake frequency increased with of frequency of school/workplaces serving them ($B=0.09$, $p<0.01$). The intake also increased with perceived lack of availability of dry/canned legumes at local supermarkets ($B=0.40$, $p<0.01$). Further, having university lecturers as a source of environmental information also increased the intake ($B=0.30$, $p=0.02$), while social media as source of health information decreased the frequency intake of legumes ($B= -0.18$, $p=0.048$).

Frequency of having meat served at school/workplace was positively associated with frequency of **red meat** intake ($B=0.11$, $p<0.01$) and **fried red meat** intake ($B=0.14$, $p<0.01$). The intake of fried red meat also increased with each 1-unit increment of perceived lack of availability of processed red meat at local supermarkets (units from 1 to 4, 1=very easy, 4=very hard) ($B=0.29$, $p<0.01$) The intake of red meat also increased with each 1-unit increment of perceived lack of availability of unprocessed red meat at local supermarkets ($B=0.28$, $p<0.01$) and with having podcasts as a source of information ($B=0.37$, $p=0.03$), or university lecturers as a source of environmental information ($B=0.34$, $p=0.03$). University lecturers as source of environmental information also increased intake of fried red meat ($B=0.40$, $p<0.01$). Oppositely, with

health professionals as the source of health information, red meat intake frequency decreased by -0.37 ($p < 0.01$) and fried red meat intake decreased by -0.33 ($p < 0.01$).

Conclusion

Almost 9 in 10 of the participants said that they would be most likely to eat red meat at work, even though many said that their workplaces rarely served red meat, which could be explained by participants buying lunch with red meat from outside work to bring to their workplace, or by participants choosing the red meat options on the rare occasions they are served at work. It was supported by the regression analysis showing that the frequency of having meat served at school/workplace increased the frequency of both red meat and processed red meat. The regression analysis also showed that the perceived lack of availability of processed and unprocessed red meat at local supermarkets was positively associated with frequency of red meat intake, which could be due to participants consuming red meat at workplaces or in restaurants instead of buying it themselves. More than 9 out of 10 found red meat easily available at retailers, while more than 7 out of 10 thought that it was expensive. The participants on average disagreed that restaurants offered vegan/vegetarian menu options. Increased prices, decreased availability, and more information about the health and environmental effects of red meat were the highest rated enabling factors that participants thought would decrease their red meat intake, which suggest that prices could be increased even further, and that availability at retailers and workplaces could be reduced.

The frequency intake of red meat also increased with having podcasts as a source of health information, or university lecturers as a source of environmental information, suggesting that these sources would not focus on a reduction of meat intake. Oppositely, when health professionals were the source of health information, red meat intake frequency decreased.

More than half of the workplaces would never serve fruit and vegetables, which in part could be explained by the low number of workplaces serving food. However, a quarter of the workplaces would often or always serve fruits and vegetables. Frequency of having fruits and vegetables served at school/the workplace was positively associated with frequency of raw vegetable intake. The vast majority of the participants were most likely to eat fruits and vegetables at home.

More than 90% thought that fruits and vegetables were easily available at retailers, while more than 50-70% found them expensive. There was an average agreement with the statement that fruits and vegetables were easy to find in the local food shops or at restaurants. The participants would prefer reduced prices on fruits and vegetables to facilitate an increased intake of those foods, while they would also like them to become more available, indicating that prices at retailers could be reduced, and – since they are already highly available at retailers – availability elsewhere such as workplaces could be increased. This was supported by the regression analysis showing that fresh fruit intake frequency decreased per 1-unit increment of perceived expensiveness of canned/frozen fruits and vegetables sold at local supermarkets. However, the frequency increased with perceived expensiveness of fresh fruits and vegetables, which might be explained by other factors than price playing a role in consumption, or that those who eat and seek out fresh fruit have higher expectations about their availability. The intake of fruits and vegetables was more frequent when podcasts or university lecturers were the sources of environmental information, and when podcasts, printed articles, online articles, or health professionals were the sources of health information.

Most of the Spanish participants had legumes 1-3 times per week, while about one in ten would never eat this type of food, showing room for increasing the intake. Almost 60% of the workplaces never served legumes, which again in part could be explained by the low number of workplaces serving food. Most of the participants would also mainly eat legumes at home, while only a few ate legumes at work. The regression analysis showed that legume intake increased when the frequency of school/workplaces serving them increased. More than 9 out of 10 found legumes to be easily available at retailers, while they were rated as the most affordable of the listed food types. The intake increased with as the perceived lack of availability of dry/canned legumes at local supermarkets increased, which could be due to factors other than availability influencing consumption, or that those who eat and seek out legumes have higher expectations about their availability. The participants themselves thought that reduced prices followed by practical skills training, and

receiving more information about the health and environmental effects would best enable them to eat more legumes. Having university lecturers as a source of environmental information also increased the intake, while social media as source of health information decreased the frequency intake of legumes, which could be due to different focuses on legumes from these sources.

3.4.5. GREECE

The Greek LL's target group was elderly people with NCDs, of all SES, aged over 60 years, in a free-living population setting.

The data were collected via a paper survey and subsequently transferred to IBM SPSS software for analysis. A total of 84 responses were included for analysis. The sample had a mean age of 68 years, ranging from 60 to 92 years. 65% of the sample were female and 35% male. Most of the participants came from urban areas (75%), while 24% came from suburban areas, and only 1 % came from rural areas.

Only 8.2 % of the participants stated that food was offered at their workplace, while 17.6% did not, and 74.1% were not employed, likely due to being retired (Figure 124). 14.1% never or rarely brought their own food to work, while 9.5% often or always did (Figure 125).

Figure 122. Greece LL food offer at work. Numbers represent percentages.

Figure 123. Greece LL food habits. Numbers represent percentages

High Impact Behaviours

The Greek Living Lab focused on the following four high impact behaviours, which will be presented separately below:

1. F&V – Eat 5 servings of vegetables and fruits per day
2. Legumes – Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)
3. HFSS – Limit the consumption of ultra-processed food products high in fat, salt, and sugar
4. Salt – Limit salt (<1500 mg/day or 2/3 of a teaspoon)

F&V – Eat 5 servings of vegetables and fruits per day

The Greek participants had a fairly high intake of fruits and vegetables, as about half (55.3%) had cooked vegetables 4-6 times per week, about half (48.2% and 51.8%) had raw vegetables or fresh fruit 2-3 times per day (Figure 126). About one in five (18.8%) only had cooked vegetables 1-3 times per week.

Figure 124. Greece LL consumption of F&V. Numbers represent percentages

Only 2.4% of the total sample said that their workplace often or always served vegetables (Figure 127), but it should be noted that it was only 8.2% of the workplaces that even served food, as mentioned above. The majority of the participants would be most likely to eat their fruits and vegetables at home (96.5%), with a big difference between intake there and at the second most likely place, which was family/friends' homes (18.8%) (Figure 128).

Figure 125. Greece LL F&V served at work. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 126. Greece LL F&V food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

The main enabler towards eating even more fruits and vegetables would be to know more about their health and environmental effects, as reported by 77.6% of the participants. With a drop down to 44.7% and 20.0% were the following enablers, namely reduced prices and increased availability (Figure 129).

Figure 127. Greece LL enablers of consuming F&V. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Legumes – Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)

About two out of three of the Greek participants had legumes 4-6 times per week (69.4%), which means that depending on the portion sizes, they could actually be within the HIB aim of three servings per week.

Figure 128. Greece LL consumption of legumes. Numbers represent percentages

For those who had food served at their workplace, 4.7% of the total sample said that they would never be served legumes, and only 2.4% would have them served sometimes or often (Figure 131). Every single one of the participants would also be most likely to eat their legumes at home (100.0%), while there is a big drop down to the second most likely place, which is friends and families' homes (11.8%), suggesting that legumes are not served to guests (Figure 132).

Figure 129. Greece LL F&V served at work. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 130. Greece LL F&V food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

Receiving more information about the health and environmental effects of legumes would help 68.2% to eat more legumes, followed by reduced prices (38.8%) and practical skills (20.0%) (Figure 133).

Figure 131. Greece LL enablers of consuming F&V. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

HFSS – Limit the consumption of ultra-processed food products high in fat, salt & sugar

Depending on the type of sweet/savoury food high in fat, sugar and/or salt, the percentages of the participants who ate them 1-3 times per week ranged from 11.8 to 38.8 (Figure 134). The proportion of those who consumed such food frequently also varied a lot, with 3.6 to 23.5 % having these types of foods 4-6 times a week.

Figure 132. Greece LL consumption of HFSS. Numbers represent percentages

For those who had food served at their workplace, 4.7% of the total sample said that they would often or always be served sweet and savoury foods such as snacks and ready-made meals, while only 1.2% would never have them served (Figure 135). The majority would be most likely to eat these foods at home (80.0%), followed by restaurants/cafes (49.4%) and friends/families' homes (42.4%) (Figure 136).

Figure 133. Greece LL HFSS served at work. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 134. Greece LL HFSS food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

Also for sweet and savoury foods, receiving more information about their health and environmental effects was by far the most often chosen enabler, in this case by 78.8% of the sample. This enabler was by far more popular than the following enablers of increased prices (32.9%) and decreased availability (31.8%) came second and third (Figure 137).

Figure 135. Greece LL enablers of consuming HFSS. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Salt – Limit salt (<1500 mg/day or 2/3 of teaspoon)

Almost one in ten would have salty snacks 4-6 times per week, while 4.8 % would eat them daily. 57.8% never or rarely ate these types of salty foods (Figure 138).

Figure 136. Greece LL consumption of salt. Numbers represent percentages

For those who had food served at their workplace, 4.7% of the total sample said that they would often be served salty snacks at work, while 2.4% would never have them served (Figure 139). Slightly more would eat salty snacks at restaurants/cafes (48.2%) than at home (41.2%) (Figure 140).

Figure 137. Greece LL salt served at work. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 138. Greece LL salt food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

For all the four HIBs chosen by the Greek LL, the most often chosen enabler was receiving more information about the health and environmental effects of the foods, and as such also for the salty foods (78.8%) (Figure 141). There was a gap down to the following enablers, which were increased prices (25.9%) and decreased availability (24.7%).

Figure 139. Greece LL enablers of consuming salt. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Perception of food environments

Many perceived healthy foods as legumes and fruits and vegetables as most easily available (Figure 142) and were also viewed as more affordable (Figure 143), but more unhealthy foods as sweets and crisps and sugary drinks were also easy to find in the participants' local food shops. Fresh fish and plant-based alternatives

were least available and viewed as expensive, highlighting challenges in accessing and being able to afford alternative protein sources.

Figure 140. Greece LL perceived availability. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 141. Greece LL perceived prices. Numbers represent percentages

Confirming the findings above, the highest rated statement about their local supermarkets were that seasonal fruits and vegetables were easy to find (4.45) (Figure 144). While the plant-based options were available (3.24), there seemed to be a need for clearer labelling of those (3.29) making them easier to identify.

Figure 142. Greece LL shopping experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

Regarding the Greek participants' usual restaurants, many agreed that they valued healthy options (4.38), although these were more expensive (4.12) and were difficult to find (3.22, 3.24) (Figure 145).

Figure 143. Greece LL restaurant experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

Information sources

Health professionals were the main source of information about health effects of food for 61.2% of the participants, which could be linked to the older age of the target group. Interestingly, 28.2% said that they also received information about environmental effects of food from health professionals (Figure 146). Online articles and social media also ranked high for both types of information, while friends/family would only be a source of information about health, not environmental effects.

Figure 144. Greece LL information sources. Participants were allowed to choose several options. Numbers represent percentages.

Regression analysis

Receiving health information ($B = -0.65$, $p = 0.32$) or environmental information ($B = -0.92$, $p = 0.01$) from online articles was associated with less frequent intake of **cooked vegetables**, while receiving health information from commercial communications ($B = 0.83$, $p = 0.049$), or from health professionals ($B = 0.61$, $p = 0.02$) was associated with an increase in consumption of cooked vegetables. Environmental information from printed articles was associated with a more frequent intake of cooked vegetables ($B = 0.73$, $p = 0.04$). The frequency of **fruit** intake increased when online articles was a source of health information ($B = 1.26$, $p < 0.01$), and when commercial communications were a source of environmental information ($B = 1.62$, $p = 0.04$). Perceived lack of availability of canned or frozen fruits and vegetables at local supermarkets was associated with a decreased intake frequency of **raw vegetables** ($B = -0.40$, $p = 0.03$). Health information from friends/family ($B = 0.58$, $p = 0.03$) and online articles ($B = 0.74$, $p = 0.04$) were associated with more frequent raw vegetable consumption, while health information from podcasts was associated with less frequent consumption ($B = -0.61$, $p = 0.049$).

Perceived lack of availability of sugary drinks in local supermarkets was associated with a decreased intake frequency of **fast-food** ($B = -0.48$, $p = 0.3$), whereas perceived expensiveness of sugary drinks was associated with an increased intake of fast-food ($B = 0.27$, $p = 0.03$) per 1-unit increment. Printed articles as a source of environmental information was associated with an increased intake of fast-food ($B = 0.63$, $p = 0.12$), of **snacks like biscuits and cakes** ($B = 0.97$, $p = 0.04$) and of **chocolate snacks** ($B = 1.08$, $p = 0.02$). As environmental information sources, podcasts ($B = 0.60$, $p = 0.01$) were associated with an increased intake frequency of **salty snacks**, while online articles ($B = -0.70$, $p = 0.03$) and social media ($B = -0.49$, $p = 0.04$) was associated with less frequent intake. Seeking health information from health professionals ($B = -0.50$, $p = 0.047$) and environmental information from social media ($B = -0.57$, $p = 0.03$) each decreased the intake frequency of **savoury snacks**, while environmental information from printed articles ($B = 0.90$, $p < 0.01$) increased the intake. Environmental information from printed articles also increased the intake of **sweet snacks** ($B = 0.94$, $p = 0.04$). Receiving

environmental information from social media was also associated with a decreased intake frequency of **snack bars** ($B = -0.47, p = 0.04$).

There were no significant results for **legumes**.

Conclusion

The majority of the participants were not employed (74%), likely due to retirement. Therefore, the main part of their reported food intake took place at home, i.e. not at work.

The Greek participants had a fairly high intake of fruits and vegetables, and the vast majority of the participants would be most likely to eat their fruits and vegetables at home (97%).

About 1 in 2 thought that reduced prices and 1 in 5 thought that increased availability would enable them to eat more fruits and vegetables. Meanwhile, healthy foods as legumes and fruits and vegetables were perceived as most easily available and as more affordable at retailers. Confirming this, the highest rated statement about their local retailers were that seasonal fruits and vegetables were easy to find, but they disagreed that these were often discounted or promoted. There was also a slight agreement that fruits and vegetables were easy to find at restaurants, though only 8% would be most likely to eat these types of foods here. The regression analysis showed that perceived lack of availability of canned or frozen fruits and vegetables at local supermarkets was associated with a decreased intake frequency of raw vegetables. The findings indicate that making fruits and vegetables more accessible and lowering their prices could encourage higher consumption of these foods.

We saw an increased frequency of fruit and/or vegetable intake when health information came from health professionals, friends/family, commercial communications, and/or online articles, or when environmental information came from printed articles or commercial communications, which suggests that these information sources emphasize fruit and vegetable intake both in terms of promoting more healthy and more environmentally sustainable diets. Meanwhile, receiving health or environmental information from online articles was associated with less frequent intake of cooked vegetables specifically, and health information from podcasts was associated with less frequent consumption of raw vegetables, which needs further exploration, especially since online articles were also associated with an increased intake of raw vegetables and fruits. Almost 8 out of 10 considered the main enabler towards eating even more fruits and vegetables was to know more about the health and environmental effects. These findings suggest that the target group could benefit from receiving more information about the effects of fruits and vegetables in order to increase their intake.

About two out of three of the Greek participants stated that they had legumes 4-6 times per week, which means that depending on the portion sizes, they could already be within the HIB aim of three servings per week. One-third thought that receiving more information about the health and environmental effects of legumes would enable them to eat even more legumes. Together with sugary drinks, legumes were perceived to be the most easily available food category at retailers. Legumes were perceived to be affordable at retailers, and four out of 10 thought that reduced prices would enable them to increase their intake of legumes. Many of the more unhealthy food categories were also perceived to be affordable, so reducing prices on legumes further to be cheaper than unhealthy alternatives might make them more appealing than unhealthy alternatives. Every single one of the participants would be most likely to eat their legumes at home, while there was a large difference between this and the second most likely place, which was friends and families' homes, chosen by 1 in 10. This suggests that legumes are not often served to guests.

8 in 10 participants would be likely to eat sweet and savoury foods at home, while almost half would be likely to eat these types of foods at restaurants/cafes and at friends/families' homes. Also for sweet and savoury foods, receiving more information about their health and environmental effects was by far the most often chosen enabler, followed by increased prices and decreased availability. The regression analysis showed that intake frequency of different types of sweet and savoury foods decreased when health information came

from health professionals, which suggests that health professionals (which were also the most popular health information source) promote limiting these unhealthy foods in a healthy diet. Intake frequency also decreased when environmental information sources were online articles and social media, while it increased when the sources were printed articles and podcasts, suggesting a different approach to or focus on these types of foods in relation to environmental effects between these sources.

Unhealthy foods such as sweets and crisps and sugary drinks were accessible in the participants' local food shops, as 8 out of 10 thought that sweets & crisps and sugary drinks were easy to find, and half thought that they were not expensive. There was a high level of agreement that unhealthy food choices were found near the retailers' cash register, and agreement that healthy options were difficult to find at restaurants. The regression analysis showed that intake frequency of fast-food decreased with perceived lack of availability of sugary drinks at retailers, which needs further exploration, since it increased with perceived expensiveness of the sugary drinks.

For the above food types, participants' homes was by far the most likely place of intake, but for salty foods, homes were surpassed by restaurants and cafes. 8 in 10 thought that receiving more information about the health and environmental effects salty foods would enable a decreased intake. The regression analysis showed that as environmental information sources, online articles and social media were associated with less frequent intake of salty snacks, while podcasts were associated with an increased intake frequency, indicating a differing approach to salty foods in relation to environmental effects between these sources.

The next most popular enablers were chosen by far fewer participants, where were increased prices and decreased availability, both chosen by about 1 in 4 of participants. Sweets and crisps were also perceived to be easily available and fairly affordable in the participants' local food shops, which suggests that there is room for increasing the prices and reducing the availability of these foods at retailers.

For all the four HIBs chosen by the Greek LL, the most often chosen enabler was receiving more information about the health and environmental effects of the foods, chosen by about 7-8 out of 10 for all four HIBs, which suggests that this target group feels an overall lack of knowledge about their diet, and that they would benefit from more information about several food groups.

3.4.6. ITALY

The Italian LL's target group was diabetic adults from low SES (low income, rural, immigrants), aged 18-70 years, in a clinical setting.

The data was collected via an online survey and subsequently transferred to IBM SPSS software for analysis. A total of 75 responses were included for analysis. The sample had a mean age of 50 years, ranging from 18 to 80 years. 71% of the sample were female and 29% male. Most of the participants (83%) came from urban areas, while 8% came from suburban and 9% from rural areas.

In 26.7% of the cases, participants' school or workplace would offer food, while this was not the case for 45.3% of the schools/workplaces (Figure 147). 37.8% would often or always bring their own food to school/workplaces (Figure 148).

Figure 145. Italy LL food offer at school/workplaces. Numbers represent percentages.

Figure 146. Italy LL food habits. Numbers represent percentages

High Impact Behaviours

The Italian Living Lab focused on the following four high impact behaviours, which will be presented separately below:

1. Meat 4 - Limit the consumption of processed meat (both red and white meat) or even avoid it
2. F&V – Eat 5 servings of vegetables and fruits per day
3. Legumes – Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)
4. HFSS – Limit the consumption of ultra-processed food products high in fat, salt, and sugar

Meat 4 - Limit the consumption of processed meat (both red and white meat) or even avoid it

38.7% of participants consumed processed meat 1-3 times a week, while this was the case for 9.3% when it came to processed poultry (Figure 149). 5.3% would eat cold cuts or other types of processed meats daily.

Figure 147. Italy LL consumption of processed meat. Numbers represent percentages

Processed meat would sometimes or often be served at school/work in 13.3% of the cases, which is also due to the relatively low number of schools/workplaces that serve food in general as presented above (Figure 150). Out of those, 13.3% would never or rarely serve processed meat. The majority would also be most likely to eat this type of food at restaurants/cafes (45.3%) or at friends/families' homes (42.7%) (Figure 151).

Figure 148. Italy LL processed meat served at school/work. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 149. Italy LL processed meat food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

Receiving more information about the health and environmental effects of processed meat was the main enabler (38.7%), followed closely by decreased availability (34.7%) and increased availability of alternatives (30.7%) (Figure 152).

Figure 150. Italy LL enablers of consuming processed meat. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

F&V – Eat 5 servings of vegetables and fruits per day

Consumption once a day was observed in 17.3-21.3% of the sample, while 20.0-24.0% had the different types of fruits and vegetables 2 times per day, indicating good adherence to dietary recommendations of eating more fruits and vegetables.

Figure 151. Italy LL consumption of F&V. Numbers represent percentages

Fruits and vegetables would sometimes or often be served at school/work in 16.0% of the cases, which is also due to the relatively low number of schools/workplaces that serve food in general as presented above (Figure 154). 8% said their workplace would never or rarely serve fruits and vegetables. The vast majority of the participants would eat their fruits and vegetables at home (90.7%) (Figure 155).

Figure 152. Italy LL F&V served at school/work. Numbers represent percentages.

Figure 153. Italy LL F&V food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Reduced prices (45.3%), increased availability (40.0%), and receiving more information (38.7%) were the main enabling factors for incorporating more fruits and vegetables into their diets (Figure 156).

Figure 154. Italy LL enablers of consuming F&V. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Legumes – Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)

About a quarter of the participants would never or rarely eat legumes (28%), while only 4% would eat them on a daily basis (Figure 157).

Figure 155. Italy LL consumption of legumes. Numbers represent percentages

Legumes would sometimes or often be served at school/work in 16.0% of the cases, which is also due to the relatively low number of schools/workplaces that serve food in general as presented above (Figure 158). 9.3% said their workplace would never or rarely serve these protein sources. Most participants would be most likely to eat legumes at home (84.0%) (Figure 159).

Figure 156. Italy LL legumes served at school/work. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 157. Italy LL legumes food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

Almost half of the sample said that gaining practical cooking skills specifically on legumes would increase their intake of these foods, followed by receiving more information and increased availability (Figure 160).

Figure 158. Italy LL enablers of consuming legumes. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

HFSS – Limit the consumption of ultra-processed food products high in fat, salt & sugar

Depending on the type of ultra-processed food, intake 1-3 times per week ranged from 10.7% (savory snacks) to 29.3% (not homemade fast food) (Figure 161). 6.7% consumed snacks like biscuits and cakes daily.

Figure 159. Italy LL consumption of HFSS. Numbers represent percentages

Sweet and savoury foods would sometimes or often be served at school/work in 16.0% of the cases, which is also due to the relatively low number of schools/workplaces that serve food in general as presented above (Figure 162). 10.7% said their workplace would never or rarely serve these ultra-processed foods. Most participants would be most likely to eat sweet and savoury foods at restaurants/cafes (52.0%) (Figure 163).

Figure 160. Italy LL HFSS served at school/work. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 161. Italy LL HFSS food environments. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options

Decreased availability (44.0%) and increased availability of alternatives (28.0%) were among the main enablers of eating less sweet and savoury foods, together with receiving more information about their health and environmental effects (34.7%) (Figure 164).

Figure 162. Italy LL enablers of consuming legumes. Numbers represent percentages. Participants were able to choose several options.

Perception of Food Environments

Different types of meat, grains, and fruits and vegetables are considered accessible (Figure 166), while fresh fish and plant-based alternatives are perceived as more expensive and less available. Other healthy categories such as nuts and fresh fruits and vegetables were also seen as most expensive (Figure 166).

Figure 163. Italy LL perceived availability. Numbers represent percentages

Figure 164. Italy LL perceived prices. Numbers represent percentages

Participants commonly agreed that unhealthy foods are often placed near the cash register (mean score of 4.04) (Figure 167). Fresh fruits and vegetables were easily available, also confirming findings presented above (3.81), but they were not often discounted or promoted (2.76).

Figure 165. Italy LL shopping experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

There was a general agreement that healthy options at restaurants were important but more expensive (both 3.47) and difficult to find (3.21). Information about the nutritional and environmental impact of food was lacking (1.79, 1.58) (Figure 168).

Figure 166. Italy LL restaurant experience. Measured on a scale from 1 – strongly disagree, to 5 – strongly agree. Numbers represent means of the total sample.

Information Sources

The main sources of health and environmental information were health professionals (28.0 and 41.3%, respectively), friends/family (0 and 38.7%, respectively), and university curriculum (24.0 and 29.3%, respectively). Podcasts were the least common source of health (9.3%) and environmental (5.3%) (information) (Figure 169).

Figure 167. Italy LL information sources. Participants were allowed to choose several options. Numbers represent percentages.

Regression analysis

When universities offered many **healthy food choices**, it was linked to increased frequency of consuming **snack bars** ($B=0.45$, $p=0.045$). When many **sustainable food choices** were offered, it was associated with an increased frequency of consuming **fast-food** ($B=0.79$, $p=0.03$).

Receiving environmental information from the university curriculum increased the intake of **chocolate- or nut-based spreads** ($B=0.53$, $p=0.44$). Friends/family as a health information source was associated with increased intake of **snacks like biscuits and cakes** ($B=0.75$, $p=0.03$), while podcasts as source of health information was linked to a decreased intake of snacks like biscuits and cakes ($B=-2.34$, $p=0.01$), and of candy snacks ($B=-2.30$, $p=0.02$). Podcasts as source of environmental information was linked to an increased frequency of consuming **candy snacks** ($B=1.61$, $p=0.02$). Commercial communications were associated with a decreased intake of candy snacks ($B=-1.48$, $p=0.02$).

The frequency of schools/workplaces serving **fruits and vegetables** was positively associated with frequency of consuming raw ($B=0.42$, $p=0.04$) and cooked vegetables ($B=0.52$, $p=0.01$). When universities offered many environmentally friendly food choices, it was linked to a decrease in consumption frequency of fresh fruit ($B=-2.46$, $p=0.04$). Intake frequency of fresh fruit was positively associated with friends/family as health information source ($B=1.29$, $p=0.01$), while podcasts as source was associated with a decrease in the frequency ($B=-3.24$, $p=0.02$). University curriculum as environmental information source increased the frequency by 1.99 ($p<0.01$).

The consumption of **raw** ($B=1.17$, $p=0.01$) and of **cooked vegetables** ($B=1.06$, $p=0.01$) was also positively associated with receiving health information from friends/family, and/or from social media (cooked, $B=1.41$, $p=0.01$), while health information from the university curriculum had a negative association with raw ($B=-1.17$, $p=0.02$) and cooked ($B=-1.03$, $p=0.02$) vegetables. *Environmental* information from university curriculum was on the other hand positively associated with intake of raw ($B=1.19$, $p<0.01$) and cooked vegetables ($B=2.18$, $p<0.01$).

Legume intake frequency was positively associated with social media ($B=0.73$, $p=0.04$) and health professionals ($B=0.58$, $p=0.04$) as a source of health information, or with university curriculum ($B=0.75$, $p=0.01$) as a source of environmental information. When health professionals were the source of environmental information, legume intake frequency decreased by -0.71 ($p=0.03$).

When podcasts were the health information source, intake frequency of **processed meat** decreased ($B= -2.20$, $p<0.01$), while the frequency increased with online articles as a source ($B=0.74$, $p=0.04$). If podcasts were the environmental information source, frequency of consuming processed meat increased ($B=1.34$, $p=0.03$). Intake frequency of **processed poultry** decreased with social media ($B= -0.37$, $p=0.01$), or with health professionals ($B= -0.28$, $p=0.02$) as health information sources, while online articles ($B=0.26$, $p=0.03$) or health professionals ($B=0.28$, $p=0.04$) as environmental information sources increased the frequency.

Conclusion

Receiving more information about the health and environmental effects of processed meat was the main enabler of reducing their consumption. The regression analysis showed that the intake frequency of processed meat decreased, when health professionals, social media, and podcasts were the health information source, and if podcasts were the environmental information source, which suggests that these sources can help enable the reduction of consumption. Meanwhile, the frequency of eating processed meat increased with online articles as a health information source, and with online articles or health professionals as environmental information sources, which could indicate that online articles do not focus on processed meat in terms of health and the environment, and neither do health professionals focus on processed meat in terms of the environment (but not health, as this decreased the intake).

The information enabler was followed closely by decreased availability of processed meat and increased availability of alternatives. We found that different types of meat were considered accessible, with more than one in six finding processed meat very easy to find at retailers. Further, there was a high level of agreement with red meat, including processed meat, being promoted at retailers. Meanwhile, fresh fish and plant-based alternatives were perceived as more expensive and less available than processed meat, indicating a lack of alternative protein sources. Since most of the participants would be likely to eat processed meat at restaurants/cafes or at friends/families' homes (and to a lesser degree their own homes), decreased availability should be considered at these places, and not only at retailers.

The findings showed a tendency of fruits and vegetables being considered easily available, though too expensive. Reduced prices and increased availability were the two main perceived enabling factors for incorporating more fruits and vegetables into the participants' diets. Different types of fruits and vegetables were considered accessible, but were also seen as most expensive - more expensive than the unhealthy food categories. Further, they were not often discounted or promoted at food stores. There was also a general agreement that healthy options at restaurants were important, but more expensive and difficult to find, and that fruits and vegetables in particular were difficult to find at restaurants. This was supported by the regression analysis showing that the frequency of schools/workplaces serving fruits and vegetables was positively associated with frequency of consuming raw and cooked vegetables. Meanwhile, when universities offered many environmentally friendly food choices, it was linked to a decrease in consumption frequency of fresh fruit. This could potentially be due to these environmentally friendly options being represented more in terms of vegetables and/or legumes replacing meat, and participants might consume less fruit as they feel their needs were met with these other options.

The third most often chosen enabler was receiving more information, and we saw that intake frequency of fruits and vegetables increased with friends/family or social media as health information source, or university curriculum as environmental information source. Meanwhile, podcasts or university curriculum as health information sources were associated with a decrease in the frequency intake, which for the university could be partly due to a lack of availability.

We saw a low intake of legumes, with about a quarter of the participants never or rarely consuming legumes, while only 4% would eat them daily. 8 in 10 participants would be most likely to eat legumes at home. Almost half of the sample said that gaining practical cooking skills specifically on legumes would increase their intake of these foods, followed by receiving more information and increased availability. Almost 7 in 10 thought that legumes were very easily accessible at retailers, and they were considered to be the most affordable of all the listed food categories. This indicates that cooking skills is a larger barrier to consumption than availability and price, at least at retailers. Increased availability could focus on settings such as restaurants/cafes, schools, and workplaces, as only 7-15% would be likely to consume them there. The regression analysis showed that legume intake frequency was positively associated with social media and health professionals as a source of health information, or with university curriculum as a source of environmental information, which suggests that these sources communicate the benefits of these legumes. When health professionals were the source of environmental information, legume intake frequency decreased, which could indicate that health professionals are focusing more on the health rather than environmental benefits.

Decreased availability and increased availability of alternatives were among the main enablers of eating less sweet and savoury foods. Sweets/crisps and refined grain products were two of three food categories perceived to be most easily available at retailers, and sweets/crisps were the second most affordable food type. Participants further commonly agreed that unhealthy foods are often placed near the cash register at food stores. Half of the participants thought they would be most likely to eat sweet and savoury foods at restaurants or cafes, and there was a general agreement that healthy options at restaurants were important but more expensive and difficult to find. These findings suggest that availability of sweet and savoury foods should focus on both retailers and restaurants/cafes. Curious findings of the regression analysis showed that when universities offered many healthy food choices, it was linked to increased frequency of consuming snack bars, but these snack bars could also be considered a healthy snack option by some. When many sustainable food choices were offered, it was associated with an increased frequency of consuming fast-food, which could be due to these fast-food options potentially having alternative proteins.

The second most often chosen enabler towards a reduction in consumption of sweet and savoury foods was receiving more information about their health and environmental effects. The regression analysis showed that receiving environmental information from podcasts or the university curriculum, or health information from friends/family, increased the intake of different types of sweet and savoury foods, which suggest that these types of environmental information sources might not be focusing on sweet and savoury foods in terms of the environment, and that friends and family might not be a good source of health information in this respect. Meanwhile, podcasts and commercial communications as sources of health information was linked to a decreased intake of certain types of sweet and savoury foods, which indicates that these might be better sources.

3.4.7. GERMANY

The German LL's target group was obese and overweight children and adolescents, aged 10-18 years, in a clinical setting.

Due to challenges with ethical approval and recruitment issues, the German LL was unable to finalize data collection in time for the analysis. Consequently, no responses from Germany were included in the analysis presented in this report.

4. Conclusion

This report has presented an analysis of how barriers and enablers influence food environments, and of how food environments shape dietary behaviour.

Part 2 – *Barriers and enablers of food chain actors to shape better food environments* - evaluated the determinants of intervention implementation aimed to promote healthy dietary behaviours in five different food environments, by involving members of five collaborative working groups (CWG) representing farmers, food industries, retailers, food services and restaurants. The barriers that CWG members experienced to the implementation of healthy food store interventions (HFI)s concerned: 1) the characteristics of consumers, their low demand for healthier and more sustainable products, the lack of consumer knowledge about the benefits of these products, 2) the lack of clear European and national guidelines to support this type of intervention, and 3) the structural and supply deficiencies of healthy and sustainable food. Traditional consumer eating habits and consumer scepticism towards the sensory appeal of healthy and sustainable food could halt decisions towards implementing HFIs, and the CWG members needed more expert support in the management of healthy and sustainable products and for making healthy and sustainable food attractive to consumers. Additional barriers included financial considerations concerning purchasing (in the case of restaurant, retailer and food service) and producing (food industry, farmers) healthy and sustainable products.

Most of the identified enablers towards HFIs belonged to the outer setting rather than the inner setting, meaning that most participants were requesting incentives or subsidies from national or EU institutions. Their willingness to adopt interventions depended on the simplicity of the implementation, and that it would not require high running costs or the acquisition of new skills and machinery. The CWGs suggested that intra- and inter-cooperation should be encouraged during the implementation of the intervention, while a strong relationship with other food actors, especially farmers, would motivate them to complete the intervention.

Many of the enablers proposed by the CWG members highlighted the need for food education campaigns for consumers. However, promoting healthy and sustainable diets requires more than just educating consumers, as their choices are shaped by the food environments in which they make decisions.

In Part 3 – *Influences of social and physical food environments on dietary behaviour* - the influence of food offer, food communication and food education on dietary behaviours was assessed by exploring factors such as availability, accessibility, affordability, acceptability, accommodation, marketing, and education. The aim was to investigate if the perceived store, restaurant, work, school, and home food environments influences participants' high impact behaviour. The findings differed across the eight living labs (LL), due to dissimilar target groups (in terms of age, life stage, health status, sample size etc.), and therefore, findings should be viewed separate to each LL, also considering that data has been collected, analysed and reported separately. The findings underscore the importance of a multifaceted approach to influence dietary behaviours positively.

When participants were asked about what would best enable them towards their consumption of a certain food or drink, availability was generally perceived to play a big role, either as decreased/increased availability of the food in question, or of its alternatives. We also saw that for some LLs, the perceived availability of the HIB food was related to the self-reported intake of same food.

The results also supported the case for improving food environments, since individualized interventions were among the least often chosen enablers across LLs. Furthermore, food was reported to be consumed in many different environments, which would heavily influence the availability and presentation of the food. Especially for the target groups that concerned children (Sweden, Poland, France), their consumption was highly influenced by what their daycares or schools served, as they would primarily eat what they served during their time there. Meanwhile, the older target groups were less influenced by the availability at schools and workplaces, since many did not attend school, and for the oldest target groups, many would be retired (namely Greece). Their access could instead be influenced by the availability at retailers, restaurants, and friends', families' and own homes.

Another commonly chosen enabler was receiving more information about the health or environmental impact of the food. Across most LLs, the participants expressed that their usual restaurants did not inform about and/or focus on sustainability aspects of the food they served, as they rarely informed about the percentage of organic ingredients, the environmental impact of the food, or the origin of the products. For the Polish LL as an example, the primary enabler to reduce meat consumption was receiving information about its health and environmental impacts. However, only half of participants indicated that their school had offered classroom teaching on nutrition and health, and one-third that their school had provided nutrient information. This indicates that schools could focus more of this information on meat impacts, possibly paired with training cooking skills for meat-free meals.

For children, the primary information sources were reported to be friends and family (likely parents) and teachers, so communication and information to this target group should go to them indirectly through their primary caretakers rather than directly through e.g. media. For the older target groups, the main information sources were online articles, social media, and health professionals, which could thus be good options for delivering information to these target groups.

Unhealthy food types such as candy, snacks, refined grains and sugary drinks were often perceived to be highly accessible and affordable at retailers. Meanwhile, adjustment of prices were often perceived to enable a positive dietary change by the participants. As we saw in Part 2, the CWGs requested incentives or subsidies from national or EU institutions to be able to improve the food environments. Such incentives could be able to improve the consumer food environment at retailers and/or restaurants, as they might be able to reduce the prices of healthy food types and increase the prices of unhealthy foods, thereby possibly affecting consumer food intake in a healthier and more sustainable direction.

The findings of the report highlight the complexity and multifaceted nature of dietary behaviours influenced by food environments, food chain actors, and consumer perceptions. Future strategies should consider how specific food environments, education and information influence consumers' dietary habits, but should also consider the food chain actors involved in these environments and the barriers and enablers that these experience towards changing these food environments.

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